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Disclaimer

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Executive Summary

The primary objective of this document is to provide a comprehensive overview of the progress made during the third year (Y3) of the SMARTNESS 2030 ERC. Following the structure and research strand organization of Y1 and Y2 scientific reports, this document emphasizes the scientific aspects, highlighting key achievements and areas for improvement. Deep technical details of the reported activities can be found in the scientific publications listed in this document and referenced throughout the description of work.

This document follows the traditional FAPESP guidelines for annual scientific reports.¹ Its structure mirrors that of the previous yearly scientific reports and is organized as follows:

- Section I provides a summary of the project as originally conceived, including an abstract, objectives, and expected results;
- Section II forms the core of the report, detailing the achievements during the reporting period. It begins with an executive overview highlighting key accomplishments and indicators, followed by a discussion of the engineering research approach and its impact. Activities are then presented per Work Package (WP) within each Research Strand (RS). Subsequent subsections briefly address related activities, including laboratory infrastructure, Education and Dissemination of Knowledge (EDK) initiatives, Technology Transfer (TT) efforts, and aspects of Management, Structure, and Governance (GEO). For a more detailed account of EDK, TT, and GEO activities, readers are directed to their respective reports;
- Section III outlines the institutional support received by SMARTNESS 2030 ERC;
- Section IV provides a compilation of all publications produced during the period;
- Section V contains a list of abbreviations.

¹ This document is the public version of Yearly Scientific Report #03 (RC3), submitted in April 2026 to FAPESP. It contains the same content as the full report, excluding three administrative sections: (i) the activity plan for the upcoming period; (ii) descriptions of participation in scientific events using FAPESP funds; and (iii) references to individual scholarship summary reports.

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I. Project Summary

A. Abstract

The SMARTNESS Engineering Research Center (ERC) targets developing cutting-edge advances in communication networks and digital application services scoped in strategic areas where significant scientific and technological impacts can be achieved towards 2030, in collaboration with the cloud and networking research communities. As 5G releases roll-out and the vision on 6G is being developed, the main challenge of SMARTNESS is how to engineer (i.e. design and operate) cloud computing and network infrastructures with the adequate capabilities to empower next-generation Internet services and applications. The scope of end-to-end Internet-scale services is exceptionally broad and requires contributions from various disciplines along with large capital and human resource investments. However, the ongoing digital transformation in vertical industries and a shift towards open source network softwarization and disaggregation of infrastructures at multiple levels and protocol stack layers have opened well-scoped opportunities for accelerated innovation at unprecedented entry barriers for research enterprises based on academic and industrial partnerships. Cloud computing and network infrastructures are increasingly becoming more multidisciplinary, requiring system-oriented end-to-end views that leverage advances in Hardware (HW) for computing and networking, modern Software (SW) architectures, machine intelligence (AI/ML), user interfaces, "as a Service" consumption and new business models, among other engineering disciplines (e.g., energy efficiency and design for security). SMARTNESS aims at exploiting well-thought-out opportunities through a proper methodology based on the confluence of parallel Research Strands (RS) tailored for successful impact research and innovation at world-class levels towards the realization of challenging use cases in Internet scenarios for industry and society with a 2030 horizon view.

B. Objectives

SMARTNESS has the ambitious objective to go beyond the state-of-the-art in several networked system disciplines, clustered into five areas of Scientific and Technological Advancements (STA), namely, (i) Customized Edge Computing, (ii) Fluid Control & Data Planes, (iii) Cognitive Architectures, (iv) Trustworthiness - Security, Privacy, Safety, Ethics, and (v) Sustainability. Each STA includes specific objectives within a common theme, acting as building blocks upon which research strands (RS) are defined and executed as the chosen strategy to organize research and engineering efforts. Each RS encompasses a group of well-defined timely STA research objectives to realize exemplary use case applications. SMARTNESS will start and be supported by currently deployed technologies and infrastructures that will evolve throughout the RS execution. The SMARTNESS view on growing the technology readiness levels is based on a deep study of already existing solutions, focusing on the technical gaps and challenges to harden the initial requirements of each RS, and validate the final approach by deep experimentation with running prototypes and experimental evaluation embodied in selected pilots. Each RS has a lifecycle, where new RS are built considering outputs from previously ended RS and inputs from the updated mid- and long-term visions, external feedback from project reviewers and the scientific community, guidance from the International Advisory Board (IAB), among other forces expected to contribute to the most appropriate steering of active RS and the definition of new ones. The RS identified for the initial years of SMARTNESS are as follows: NEWTON: iN Edge netWork indusTRial automatioN, (2) DEMIST: Distributed Edge Computing Swarm Intelligence, (3) C3LA: Cognitive Closed Control Loops Architecture for Edge IoV Services, (4) ADVENTURE: Adaptive and Secure Network Applications over the Industrial Internet, and (5) DisCoNet: Distributed Computer Networking.

C. Expected Results

SMARTNESS is expected to achieve impact results in Brazil and abroad from a four-axis perspective: technological and scientific, standardization, socio-economic, and commercial.

- **International technological and scientific impact.** The results achieved by SMARTNESS will be disseminated through open source software, open data, software APIs, high-quality scientific publications in high impact vehicles, industry-academia workshops and integration with existing solutions. The dissemination activities will result in a significant increase in the number of citations to SMARTNESS scientific productions and partnerships with renowned researchers and research centers world-wide. Outcomes of each RS will be embodied in Proof of Concept (PoC) implementations validated through experimental evaluation and testbed demos.
- **Standardization impact.** SMARTNESS will contribute to selected standards development organization (e.g., ONF, IETF, ISO, ITU-T, 3GPP, ONAP, O-RAN, and ETSI) activities in terms of architectures and PoC implementations. Concepts, technical solutions, and open source software produced by SMARTNESS will contribute to the current and upcoming IP-related standards.
- **Socio-economic impact.** SMARTNESS will be the first center focused on smart networks and services in Brazil towards the realization of killer novel applications such as robotics, vehicular networks, AR/VR/XR, holographic communication, all of them natively integrated with ML and cognitive artifacts. All of these areas are key to the future of technological innovation in the country as they are directly related to the future of mobile telecommunications networks towards 6G, which should shape the services and applications of telecom companies in the coming years. The training of human resources undergraduate, graduate, including interactions with mid/high school students, will generate new careers in the upfronting areas and positively impact the local ecosystem, both in terms of improvement of services available to the population and new opportunities for young researchers in São Paulo and Brazil.
- **Commercial impact.** It is expected that part of the results achieved by SMARTNESS will be absorbed by governments and industries, especially in the B5G ecosystem, certainly but not limited to Ericsson units, through innovation in products, new business models, and startups. The support from additional FAPESP funding lines, in the form of the PIPE and PITE programs that can be incubated within the SMARTNESS center, will contribute to the impact setting of this objective. We foresee that SMARTNESS testbed infrastructures, realistic network, and user emulation capabilities in scope of 5G and beyond could welcome hosting startups experiments for validation and stress testing of end-user and server-side software applications under realistic environments, integrated with programmable networks and the advanced network services among other expected outcomes from the ongoing research strands.

II. Achievements in the period

A. Executive Overview

As it completes its third year, the SMARTNESS ERC stands at a stage of consolidation and deeper exploration of its research, showcasing both the scientific and technological progress made and the challenges encountered along the way. This document records this trajectory, offering a detailed summary of the progress achieved during this phase. It examines the methodologies applied, the obstacles faced, and the adjustments introduced to enhance research efficiency. Additionally, it situates the achievements within the broader scientific and technological landscape, emphasizing its influence on engineering advancements and interdisciplinary collaboration. By addressing the technical and organizational dimensions of the initiative, this document provides insights into the tangible impacts generated and outlines the planned directions for the project's next steps.

To provide an overview of Y3 progress, this report is organized into the following thematic sections:

Overview of SMARTNESS Engineering Research Approach & Impact: the introduction delineates the structured organization of SMARTNESS covering distinct Scientific and Technological Advancements (STA), systematically arranged within Research Strands (RS) that serve as hosts to various Work Packages (WP). The Research Strands serve as a core organizational framework for structuring research and engineering initiatives towards focused, time-bound STA objectives, which are implemented through dedicated WPs that target use-case applications. During Y3, SMARTNESS has refined its execution strategy, adapting RS to incorporate new research demands, integrate emerging technologies, and address increasingly complex use cases. [\[Section II.B\]](#)

Research Strands activities per Work Package: this section presents the core technical activities and achievements during the third year, tracking the evolution of RS WP across different stages (completed, ongoing, newly initiated, and upcoming). Within this context, it provides a structured overview of all WPs, highlighting key research developments, team contributions, and their continuous adaptation of objectives, alongside principal findings and scientific publication results. [\[Section II.C\]](#)

Lab Infrastructures & Testbeds: this section details the advancements in establishing an experimental environment for SMARTNESS 2030 ERC. Renovations are underway to accommodate the main laboratory at LEMAC-FEEC, integrating cutting-edge measurement facilities such as a full anechoic chamber and high-frequency VNAs. Additionally, the section presents progress on the deployment of a private 5G SA network, ongoing infrastructure upgrades, and the expansion of computational and networking resources to support research activities. [\[Section II.D\]](#)

Education and Dissemination of Knowledge (EDK): this section summarizes the main efforts and accomplishments in the Year 3 EDK Report (REDK3) that explores in detail all ongoing initiatives and achievements in scientific engagement, workforce development, and outreach within the research community, including contributions to high-impact publications, participation in and organization of major scientific events, and integration of new educational resources. [\[Section II.E\]](#)

Technology Transfer (TT): this section presents an abstract of TT efforts during the third year, which are detailed in the TT Report (RTT3) and span open research, standardization, Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), research spin-offs, and technological knowledge transfer. [\[Section II.F\]](#)

Management, Structure and Governance (GEO): this section recaps the essence of the management, structure, and governance practices of SMARTNESS 2030 ERC, all of which are detailed in the Year 3 GEO report (RGEO3), covering the center's organizational framework, quality assurance protocols, risk management strategies, communication tools, and administrative procedures. The third year's efforts highlight the consolidation of the organizational structure, the

implementation of more efficient review processes, the expansion of communication channels, and the establishment of workflows that enhance internal coordination and decision-making. [\[Section II.G\]](#)

Institutional Support: this section outlines the institutional support that has strengthened SMARTNESS activities throughout its second year, including research management, administrative assistance, communication strategies, IPR management, and laboratory infrastructure. Notable developments include expanding the management team through PPDG grants, additional financial support for laboratory renovations via the InfraPeq program, and ongoing assistance from different institutional entities. [\[Section III\]](#)

List of publications. [Section IV](#) presents the **list of publications** resulting from SMARTNESS 2030 ERC activities. The reference style for the publications produced in year 03 uses the RC3 prefix followed by the publication categories indexes recommended by FAPESP reproduced below.

- A – Papers in indexed scientific periodicals
- B – Papers in non-indexed scientific periodicals
- C – Papers presented in international conferences
- D – Papers presented in Brazilian conferences
- E – Patents requested or obtained
- F – Chapters in published books
- G – Books published
- H – MSc Dissertations defended
- I – PhD Theses defended
- J – List of papers prepared, submitted, and accepted for publication

[Section V](#) provides a **List of Abbreviations** used in this report.

■ Highlights & Indicators

The third year of the SMARTNESS 2030 Engineering Research Center represented a phase of consolidation and acceleration, building on foundational progress to deliver transformative advancements in programmable networks, edge computing, immersive media, distributed intelligence, and beyond-5G infrastructures. This period saw the Center solidify its operational maturity through refined research strands WPs, unprecedented scientific output, and strategic infrastructure deployments, while markedly advancing its internationalization via FAPESP BEPE scholarships that fostered deep collaborations with global leaders in academia and industry. These efforts not only exceeded key performance indicators but also positioned SMARTNESS as a cornerstone for Brazil contributions to 5G innovation towards 6G, evidenced by high-impact publications, standardization efforts, and tangible technology transfer milestones.

A landmark achievement was the inauguration of the SMARTNESS Studio 5G (SS5G) in December 2025 at LEMAC/FEEC-UNICAMP. This state-of-the-art private 5G SA facility integrates Ericsson baseband/Radio Dots, GPU clusters, programmable switches for high-precision traffic and network emulation, enabling end-to-end validation of XR and volumetric media streaming, among other PoCs. Showcased during the Ericsson Research Open Day and FAPESP visits, SS5G has already fueled national and international collaborations.

Scientific production surged, with Year 3 yielding 68 published outputs, including 10 indexed journal articles, 40 international conference papers, and 14 Brazilian conference contributions, alongside 18 accepted and 29 submitted works, bringing cumulative totals to 135 publications across three years. Breakthroughs spanned all Research Strands, to cite a few: DisCoNet XR model partitioning and O-RAN slicing, DECOMPOSER framework at IEEE NOMS, NEWTON programmable data planes and IoRT platforms; C3LA volumetric media QoE metrics (e.g., Best Demo Award at IEEE NetSoft); DEMIST drone fleet coordination and federated learning for telco; and a new RS call NEXT to incubate research on security, quantum/semantic explorations, and hardware metasurfaces. Three MSc theses and one PhD dissertation were defended, underscoring workforce development amid a thriving ecosystem of 7 postdocs, 27 PhD, 28 MSc, and 27 undergrad scholars across 17 institutions.

Dissemination efforts amplified visibility through website items, newsletters, social media posts, short videos, and the weekly SMARTNESS Hours. Open science thrived new public datasets and GitHub repos along with Zenodo/REDU archiving. Standardization efforts included Brazilian ISO/ITU-T SC29, ITU-T SG21 experts on GS encoding, and ABNT/ANATEL roles, while TT advanced with one patent filed on application deployment in heterogeneous HW, 3 cumulative filings, and spin-off frameworks.

Noteworthy to Year 3 was the internationalization strategy, propelled by FAPESP BEPE scholarships that enabled multiple PhD (e.g., ER Kista, LiU, UvA, AAT, Cardiff), MSc (UC3M, imec-Gent, TU-Berlin), and IC (UvA) stays. A highlight goes to intensified collaboration with two PhD students working in Kista at Ericsson headquarters. The research abroad stays contributed to high-quality joint papers (e.g., AAMAS'26), upstream open source contributions, and bidirectional tech and knowledge transfer. This influx of global expertise enhanced WP roadmaps, diversified methodologies, and amplified citations, embodying SMARTNESS push-pull academia-industry model.

GEO maturation featured full management team, improved workflows, weekly EC/STAB meetings, and risk-optimized processes, streamlining IPR, publications, and quarterly Ericsson reports. Institutional backing via PRP/FUNCAMP sustained this momentum, setting Y4 for WP refreshes, journal publication pushes, and expected expansion through new funding sources.

Tables 1 to 5 present key performance indicators (KPIs) and impact targets, along with their status after Year 2, across different strategic areas to assess the success as originally envisioned.

Table 1. Dissemination & exploitation impact-setting activities and KPIs in Y3 and total since Y1.

Activity	Realized in Y3	Total (Y1 + Y2 + Y3)
Scientific Publications	10 scientific periodicals 40 international conferences 14 Brazilian conferences	15 scientific periodicals 75 international conferences 34 Brazilian conferences
Open Source Software	10 public repositories	15+ repositories
Open Data Repository	02 new datasets: 3GPP LLM [RC3.C05] and SBRC 2026 [RC3.J18] available at https://github.com/EricssonResearch/telemetry_sbrc_2026/tree/main	05 datasets
Standardization	01 leadership position: Brazilian HoD (Head of Delegation) of ISO/ITU-T SC29. 02 participations as experts in ISO/ITU-T SC29/ ITU-T SG21 standardization meetings. 02 leadership positions: Vice-Chair of ITC (IEEE ComSoc & ISOC), Executive Coordinator of IT at USP 04 participations in standardization committees (ABNT & ANATEL) 01 quality system implementation: ISO 17025:2017 for research & TT	<i>Idem</i> Y3
Intellectual Property	01 patent filed	01 IVD submitted 02 patents filed
Spin-offs pitches	1 spin-off framework (under development)	<i>Idem</i> Y3
Collaboration with startups	NTR (Nothing To Report)	01 Support letter to PITE submission

Table 2. Publication KPIs per type and status in Y3 and total after the first three years.

Publication Type / Status	Published Y3	Accepted Y3	Submitted Y3	Total (Y1-Y3)
A) Papers in indexed scientific periodicals	10	0	10	15
B) Papers in non-indexed scientific periodicals	0	0	0	0
C) Papers in international conferences	40	9	9	75
D) Papers in Brazilian conferences	14	9	11	34
E) Patents	0	0	1	3
F) Book Chapters	0	0	0	3
G) Books	0	0	0	0
H) MSc Dissertations defended	3			6
I) PhD Theses defended	1			2
Total	68	18	31	138

Table 3. Dissemination activities in the scope of the communication plan and KPIs.

Activity	Target KPI	Realized in Y3
Website content	At least 5 new content items/month; 1 whitepaper/year summarizing the main achievements/progress report	36 Posts on News 03 Postdoctoral Opportunities 01 PhD Scholarship Opportunity 01 Press release 03 Newsletters 01 Events
Webinars, podcasts and short videos	6 / year, with researchers from the consortium or outside 1 institutional video about the Center	15 short videos
Social media dissemination	At least 4 posts/month in social media	49 Posts on Facebook 63 Posts on Instagram 80 Posts in LinkedIn 61 Posts in Twitter 35 SMARTNESS Hour

Table 4. Scientific & Educational Events impact setting activities and KPIs.

Activity	Target KPI	Realized in Y3
Summer Schools	At least 1 / year, co-located with national/international conferences or on the premises of the Universities / Ericsson	Bootcamp conducted during the week of the Y3 workshop.
Hackathons (Technological + Educational)	2 / year, co-located with national/international conferences or on the premises of the Universities / Ericsson	NTR (Nothing To Report)
Open Scientific Challenge	1 every two years. Public with worldwide participation	NTR (Nothing To Report)
One-day workshops (Technological + Educational)	2 / year, co-located with national/international conferences and/or on the premises of the Universities / Ericsson	01 SBRC 2025 Workshop de Redes Quânticas (WQuNets) 01 Year 2 Workshop (Apr/2025)
Co-Organization and Participation in scientific events	At least 3 per year per Research Strand	15 Participation of SMARTNESS in events.
Participation in renowned industrial exhibitions	At least 1 / year (depending on the industrial exhibitions agenda)	6G Briefing 2025 Futurecom 2025
Ericsson Research Open Day	1 every two years, open house day at Ericsson in Brazil (São Paulo or Indaiatuba)	Talk + demos at Ericsson Research in Indaiatuba (Fev/2026)

Table 5. Teaching, Training & Workforce Development activities and KPIs.

Activity	Target KPI	Realized in Y3
Teaching: New/adapted academic courses	At least 20 courses will be impacted or created, both graduate and undergraduate	02 postgraduate courses 01 short course
Teacher training	1 every two years, short seminars for pre-college teachers	NTR (<i>Nothing To Report</i>)
Pre-college in-class and out-of-class activities	1 / year, short seminars to pre-college students	1 pre-college program/education & dissemination project launched (Dr. Telêmaco Paioli Melges State School)
FAPESP São Paulo School of Advanced Science	1 every three years	NTR (<i>Nothing To Report</i>)
Workforce Development	On average, per RS (approx. 5 active in parallel at any given time): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 Postdoc (PD) per year, • 2 PhD (DR) every 4 years, • 2 MSc (MS) every 2 years, • 1 Undergrad (UG) project per year 	03 MSc defenses 01 PhD defense Active scholarships during Y3: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PD: 07 • DR: 28 • MS: 28 • UG: 27

B. SMARTNESS Engineering Research Approach & Impact

The SMART Networks and ServiceS for 2030 (SMARTNESS) Engineering Research Center (ERC) has the ambition to go beyond the state-of-the-art networked system disciplines that can be clustered into five major areas of Scientific and Technological Advancements (STA), namely, (i) Customized Edge Computing, (ii) Fluid Control & Data Planes, (iii) Cognitive Architectures, (iv) Trustworthiness - Security, Privacy, Safety, Ethics, and (v) Sustainability. As shown in Figure 1, the scope of SMARTNESS includes STA, regarded as enablers of future applications relevant to society and industry in the horizon of 2030 and the 6G time frame. The vision of SMARTNESS is to structure STAs that gather specific, ambitious objectives within a common theme, acting as building blocks upon which Research Strands (RS) are defined and executed.

Figure 1. Main areas of Scientific and Technological Advancements (STA) in the scope of SMARTNESS.

At execution time, RS act as organizational thrusts that host the work packages (WP) where the actual scientific and technological contributions in the different STAs are realized. WPs include target application domains and scenarios that challenge the state of the art in each STA realm. Figure 2 shows the SMARTNESS execution strategy based on Research Strands (RS) to organize research and engineering efforts. Each RS encompasses a group of well-defined, timely STA research objectives described in Work Packages (WP) to carry out tasks towards the realization of exemplary use case applications. SMARTNESS will start and be supported by currently deployed technologies and infrastructures evolving throughout the RS execution.

Figure 2. SMARTNESS RS / WP Management Structures and lifecycle. The left side illustrates the initial set-up with “independent” RS WPs. The right side illustrates the aggregation of RSs into new WPs to cope with more complex use cases and/or strengthen the results.

As described in the FAPESP ERC proposal of SMARTNESS, the bootstrapping RS proposed for the initial years are as follows:

- NEWTON: In Edge netWork indusTrial automation
- C3LA: Cognitive Closed Control Loops Architecture for Edge IoV Services
- DisCoNet: Distributed Computer Networking
- DEMIST: Distributed Edge Computing Swarm Intelligence
- ADVENTURE: Adaptive and Secure Network Applications over the Industrial Internet

As shown in Figure 3, the five RS presented in the original plan of the ERC serves to illustrate how research activities were expected to be effectively carried out within SMARTNESS. The description of RS served to motivate challenging application use case scenarios along with the research methodology towards the realization of concrete objectives per STA.

Figure 3. Exemplar illustration of SMARTNESS RS lifecycle and strawman effort distribution per STA. Not shown for clarity are the transfer/re-use of milestones across RS work packages.

As expected from any 10-year research-centric initiative, different forces were expected to contribute to the most appropriate steering of RS at run-time along with the motivation to define new RS. The SMARTNESS view on growing the technology readiness levels is based on continuous monitoring of research developments, assessments of existing solutions, and identification of technical gaps and research challenges viable to be tackled through Work Packages (WPs).

Acting as a research management structure, each RS has a natural lifecycle, where new RS is built considering outputs from previously ended RS and inputs from the updated mid- and long-term visions, external feedback from project reviewers and the scientific community, guidance from the International Advisory Board (IAB), among other research & development & innovation forces that influence WPs within RS.

Each WP takes into consideration the availability of an adequate team of investigators and students to carry out up-to-date STA objectives after a proper assessment of the state-of-the-art. Depending on the nature and size of each WP, adequate research methodology will be applied, eventually including the development of prototype implementations, testbed experiments, and evaluation of embodiments in selected pilots.

After three years of activities in the Center, we confirm that a comprehensive way of understanding our mode of operation is to draw an analogy to a push-pull strategy applied to academia-industry research collaboration. A pull system initiates production as a reaction to present demand, whereas a push system initiates production in anticipation of future demand.

Figure 4. SMARTNESS Push-Pull model for Academia-Industry Collaboration

As illustrated in Figure 4, Academic Research *Push* brings new research findings, ideas, trends, etc., from SMARTNESS to Ericsson Research and other stakeholders at a national and international scope. In the other direction, Industry & Community / Ericsson *Pull* has exercised through the sharing of new research demands/opportunities from related research projects (e.g. EU SNS JU) and/or standardization efforts (e.g. O-RAN, 3GPP) brought to SMARTNESS with the objective of provoking relevant contributions after shaping ongoing Research Strand WPs and/or creating new ones. Both the Push and Pull thrusts are carefully curated by the EC, and where appropriate, guided by interactions with members of our scientific STA board (STAB) and international advisory board (IAB).

The original impact plan of SMARTNESS is evolving as expected, with the Center poised to exert a significant influence on both the Brazilian and global contexts. Figure 5 illustrates our impact-setting approach, encompassing a multifaceted strategy including public policy, startup ventures, and societal impact, all guided by tailored exploitation plans.

Figure 5. SMARTNESS Impact Setting

C. Research Strand Activities per Work Package

This section reviews core technical activities and achievements across all Research Strands (RS) Work Packages (WPs) after Year 3 (Y3). Per SMARTNESS's operational model, some WPs (e.g., NW1, CL1, DM1) completed their planned two-year lifecycles, while others span various stages: newly started (e.g., CL3), midway (e.g., DC4), final stretch (e.g., DC1–DC3) before refresh (e.g., DC5–DC7 with core teams intact but updated objectives), or emergent (e.g., NW4 from NW1).

Reported scope varies by WP maturity, team composition, and prior progress. As 3GPP advances 6G use cases and KPIs (e.g. 3GPP TR 22.870), WPs continuously update scenarios and performance targets. Y3 highlights include CL3's pivot to immersive media standardization, anticipating 6G growth in networking/compute challenges for industrial/societal use cases, and sustained UAV/drone/robotics momentum across verticals.

To address evolving demands, SMARTNESS introduced NEXT, a new "WP Incubator" RS for technology scouting and competence building into strategic research topics (e.g., quantum, semantic communication, etc.).

Table 6 provides a timeline of active RS WPs (Q1'24–Q4'27). For readability and conciseness, a standardized naming convention has been adopted to uniquely identify each WP. This convention uses a two-letter prefix representing the RS, followed by the WP number. For example, WP1 of the NEWTON RS is labeled NW1, WP1 of the C3LA RS is CL1, WP1 of DisCoNet is DC1, and so on.

Table 6. Overview of all currently active WPs, considering the period from Q1/2024. Completed quarters of WP are colored in red while upcoming quarters are in green.

RS WP#. Short Name	2024				2025				2026				2027			
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4												
NW2. Internet of Robotic Things for smart enterprises																
NW3. Distributed perception at the TROCA environment																
NW4. Programmable data plane																
CL3. Immersive Media																
DC1. Disaggregation and edge offloading of XR & ML models																
DC2. WebAssembly Edge Offloading of Browser Apps																
DC3. O-RAN and intelligent decision-making based on DL																
DC4. LLM-enabled control with dynamic compute AI offloading																
DM2. Edge-assisted intelligent drone management																
DM3. Efficiency of Federated Learning in telco scenarios																
AD1. Distributed Intelligence for Secure 6G Network Services																
AD2. Blockchain-based governance mechanisms																
NEXT: WP Incubator (e.g. AI1)																

■ DisCoNet — Distributed Computer Networking

[WP id. Title]	Academic Team [Role: Name (Institution)]	Ericsson Team [Name (Research Area)]
DC1. Disaggregation and offloading of XR applications and ML models to the edge	PI: Prof. Fabio L. Verdi (UFSCar) Co-PI: Prof. Sand Luz Corrêa (UFG) PhD 1: Guilherme Mendes Vieira de Matos (UFSCar) PhD 2: Washington Silva (UFSCar)	Andrew Williams (RA Compute & Software)
DC2. WebAssembly Edge Offloading of Browser User Apps	PI: Prof. Sand Luz Corrêa (UFG) Co-PI: Prof. Fábio L. Verdi (UFSCar) Co-PI: Prof. Cristiano Both (Unisinos) Co-PI: Prof. Bruno Silvestre (UFG) UR 1: Gabriel Nery da Silva Espindola (UFG) UR 2: Matheus Lucas Moraes Pires (UFG) MSc: Gustavo Jardim (Unisinos)	Andrew Williams (RA Compute & Software), Hector Caltenco (RA Hardware, devices and EMF)
DC3. O-RAN and intelligent decision-making based on distributed learning mechanisms	PI: Prof. Flávio Geraldo Coelho Rocha (UFG) Co-PI: Prof. Kleber Vieira Cardoso (UFG) Co-PI: Prof. Cristiano Both (Unisinos) Co-PI: Prof. Fábio L. Verdi (UFSCar) Co-PI: Prof. Leandro Almeida (UFSCar) PhD 1: Sergio Rossi B. da Silva (UNICAMP) PhD 2: Paulo Eduardo Camera (UNISINOS) MSc: Vlademir Brusse (UFSCar) UR 1: Marcus Vinícius Caruso Leite (UFSCar) UR 2: Murillo Pires Teixeira Mello (UFG)	Igor Almeida, André M. Cavalcante, Maria V. Marquezini (RA Networks)
DC4. LLM-enabled control with dynamic compute offloading of AI modules	PI: Prof. Fabio Verdi (UFSCar) Co-PI: Prof. Kleber Vieira Cardoso (UFG) Co-PI: Prof. Sand Luz Corrêa (UFG) UR 1: Gabriel Nery da Silva Espindola (UFG) UR 2: Matheus Lucas Moraes Pires (UFG) UR 3: Felipe Bonadia Bravo (UFSCar) UR 4: João Vitor Naves Mesa (UFSCar) UR 5: Rebeca Cabral (IFPB)	Ricardo Souza (RA AI)

DC1: Disaggregation and edge offloading of XR apps & ML models

The DC1 WP investigates how specialized hardware accelerators and disaggregated compute resources can support the demanding requirements of AR/VR applications and associated machine learning workloads. The WP addresses the limitations of CPU-only processing in meeting real-time demands for immersive XR services, which require accurate physical-virtual object integration and intensive ML inference. By leveraging programmable devices such as SmartNICs, GPUs, DPUs, and FPGAs, the work aims to advance the state-of-the-art in compute distribution optimization across heterogeneous edge environments while preserving low-latency performance.

The research goal of DC1 is to develop model partitioning, profiling, and deployment strategies that effectively distribute XR and ML workloads across specialized hardware while accounting for network constraints and inter-device load balancing.

The adopted methodology combines WebAssembly-based distributed systems, DAG-based profiling algorithms, operation fusion optimization, and hardware-aware solver design.

The main activities and achievements in this period can be summarized as follows:

- Design and implementation of DECOMPOSER [RC3.C02] presented at IEEE NOMS 2025, a mechanism designed to decompose monolithic applications into modular components, allowing them to be executed across various combinations of hardware architectures;
- Contribution to the AORTA project through implementation of a distributed WebAssembly system, with associated research paper submitted for publication [RC3.J46];
- Initiation of Machine Learning kernels implemented in WebAssembly, applying specialized knowledge gained through Ericsson Research collaboration;
- Advancement of the DAG profiling algorithm to support diverse model architectures;
- Implementation of framework enhancements including operation fusion performance remodeling, hardware-dependent solver updates, network impact modeling, and inter-device load balancing constraints;
- Two papers accepted at Sigmetrics 2026 Student Research Competition:
 - “SPARX: A Resource-aware Partitioning Framework for Distributed Inference on Heterogeneous Devices” [RC3.J23]
 - “Toward End-to-End Adaptive Application Decomposition and Execution Across Distributed Computing Infrastructures” [RC3.J24].
- Successful PhD qualification defenses:
 - Washington Silva defended his PhD qualification exam with the title: “Delivering Augmented Reality to the Edge: An Approach Toward Model Partitioning Across Heterogeneous Devices.”
 - Guilherme Matos defends his PhD qualification exam with the title: “Functional decomposition of monolithic applications into heterogeneous hardware.”
- Two ongoing PhD research abroad stays (BEPE scholarships): PhD student Washington Silva at Cardiff University and Guilherme Matos at Ericsson Research Kista, contributing to deeper knowledge and technology transfer between SMARTNESS and Ericsson as well as strengthening international collaboration of academic excellence;
- One patent applications filed:
 - “Deploying Applications Across Heterogeneous Computing Resources” [RC3.E01].

As described in [Section IV](#) on future period activities, the DC1 work plan has been renewed and will be continued, driven by its core team within the DC5 WP.

DC2: WebAssembly Edge Offloading of Browser User Apps

DC2 investigates WebAssembly (Wasm) as a lightweight and portable execution substrate for computational offloading from resource-constrained user devices to network edge servers, with a particular focus on latency-sensitive XR applications. The WP leverages WebAssembly's low runtime overhead, strong isolation guarantees, hardware portability, and efficient sandboxed execution to enable seamless application component migration across the device-edge continuum.

The research goal of this WP is to design, implement, and validate a WebAssembly-based offloading framework that supports dynamic workload migration and standardized edge integration. The research focuses on XR applications, whose processing pipelines typically involve latency-sensitive and computationally intensive components. The adopted methodology combines framework development, 3GPP EDGEAPP architecture integration, Kubernetes orchestration evaluation, and experimental validation on 5G testbeds.

The main activities and achievements in this period can be summarized as follows:

- Development and evaluation of mechanisms to support efficient computational offloading of XR workloads using WebAssembly across the device–edge continuum. A lightweight WebAssembly-based offloading framework was designed and implemented, enabling application components to dynamically migrate from resource-constrained devices to edge servers. A proof-of-concept prototype based on a 2D object detection pipeline was developed and a demonstration paper was published at IEEE NOMS 2025 [RC3.C10];
- Integration of this offloading framework with the 3GPP EDGEAPP architecture, enabling WebAssembly modules to be securely offloaded and executed in edge data networks through standardized discovery, authentication, and connectivity procedures;
- Experimental validation on a 5G testbed demonstrated successful end-to-end integration without introducing performance penalties when compared to container-based deployments. As a result of this activity, a paper is currently under review at IEEE Communications Magazine [RC3.J12];
- Investigation of orchestration strategies for WebAssembly workloads in Kubernetes clusters by evaluating three deployment approaches: standalone Wasm applications running directly on the host, Docker containers, and Wasm containers. As a result of this activity, a paper was accepted to SBRC 2026 [RC3.J13];
- Validation of the proposed offloading framework for more complex AI workloads by extending the system to support 3D object detection tasks, particularly using the Cube R-CNN model with a PyTorch backend through the WASI-NN interface. As part of this effort, GPU support was contributed upstream to the open source Wasmtime project.²

DC3: End-to-end slicing in latency-sensitive networks

DC3 investigates resource allocation and network slicing mechanisms for latency-sensitive applications running over Open RAN architectures. The WP addresses the need for closed-loop control in disaggregated 5G environments, where transport, radio, and core functions must be coordinated to meet stringent delay requirements for mission-critical services. Its scope includes the transport network interconnecting O-RAN functional units, synchronization support, and the integration of slicing and scheduling mechanisms across heterogeneous network resources.

The research goal of this WP is to design and evaluate low-latency control mechanisms that remain compatible with O-RAN and 3GPP principles while enabling scalable and adaptive optimization of end-to-end service delivery. The considered scenario jointly incorporates multiple network dimensions, including heterogeneous slices, routing paths, transmission capacities, diverse application requirements, and a large number of UEs.

The adopted methodology combines disaggregated OpenAirInterface (OAI) deployments, P4/Tofino programmable data plane devices, distributed learning, queueing-theoretic modeling, and testbed-based experimentation. This includes the use of Tofino hardware switches for transport control, RF-based UE emulation, precision synchronization mechanisms, and AI-driven control loops deployed through the near-real-time RIC.

The main activities and achievements in this period can be summarized as follows:

- Consolidation of an ANFIS-based proposal for transport network resource allocation in a disaggregated OAI 5G RAN with a midhaul composed of two Intel Tofino switches [RC3.C24];
- Implementation of a proof-of-concept six-node topology in which each node runs a local ANFIS agent for transmission allocation, coordinated by a federated learning entity that drives global behavior [RC3.C24];

² <https://github.com/bytedcodealliance/wasmtime/pull/10204>

- Extension of the study to an Industry 4.0 scenario, including latency analysis and comparison against static sharing, FRBS, and standalone ANFIS baselines [\[RC3.J31\]](#);
- Investigation of synchronization mechanisms in programmable data plane devices and integration of Time Sensitive Networking features on Intel Tofino switches [\[RC3.C15\]](#), including support for Credit-Based Scheduling [\[RC3.J30\]](#);
- Development of AI and ML-based algorithms to control TSN scheduling within Open RAN through the near-RT RIC using the FlexRIC platform [\[RC3.J30\]](#);
- Initial investigation of L4S integration in transport and RAN networks, including security analysis of unresponsive ECN attacks that may starve compliant low-latency traffic [\[RC3.J15\]](#);
- Implementation and ns-3 evaluation of L4S in 5G RLC layer downlink buffer, demonstrating significant reductions in queueing delay during high-demand resource competition [\[RC3.C39\]](#);
- Ongoing experiments integrating 5G networks with TSN-enabled transport, focusing on Time-Aware Shaping and dynamic Gate Control List control in a real testbed environment.

DC4: LLM-enabled control with dynamic compute offloading of AI modules

This WP addresses the use of large and small AI models in networked control systems, with a focus on dynamic compute offloading, AI module partitioning, and the use of intelligent agents for network interaction. The WP is structured around two complementary fronts: one centered on offloading AI modules and exploring LLM/VLM partitioning strategies, and another focused on network agent APIs for interacting with 5G core capabilities. These themes reflect the broader challenge of integrating AI reasoning and control functions into latency-sensitive and resource-constrained network environments.

The research goal of this WP is to determine how AI models can be decomposed, deployed, and orchestrated across heterogeneous compute environments while preserving acceptable performance, efficiency, and responsiveness. The adopted methodology combines empirical model evaluation, optimization-oriented formulation, and testbed-based experimentation. On the AI-offloading side, the work investigates multi-task learning as an alternative to single-task learning for 5G RAN modeling, using datasets with different temporal and structural properties. On the network-agent side, the work evaluates whether LLM-based agents can reliably translate high-level intent into correct API interactions, using tool-augmented workflows built around the NEF Traffic Influence API and validated in a 5G core test environment.

The main activities and achievements in this period can be summarized as follows:

- Investigation of multi-task learning for 5G RAN modeling, with comparative evaluation against single-task learning under datasets with distinct temporal and structural characteristics [\[RC3.J16\]](#)[\[RC3.J21\]](#);
- Analysis of several MTL architectures, including hard parameter sharing, expert-based models, and attention-driven approaches, with Multi-gate Mixture-of-Experts emerging as the most effective trade-off between accuracy, complexity, and inference efficiency [\[RC3.J16\]](#)[\[RC3.J21\]](#);
- Development of a RL setup to train an agent to decide between local execution and offloading, with ongoing evaluations that also consider the load of edge servers;
- Formulation of a computation offloading problem based on an indoor radio-quality dataset obtained during an undergraduate BEPE scholarship at the University of Amsterdam, using a Markov Decision Process to support RL decision making;
- Exploration of AI agents for network control tasks through the NEF Traffic Influence API, assessing the ability of LLMs to convert high-level requests into valid interactions with 5G system components;
- Integration of the Model Context Protocol to connect LLMs with tools that encapsulate the NEF Traffic Influence API, enabling a tool-augmented agent workflow for network control;

- Comparative evaluation of different LLMs, including Qwen, GPT-OSS-20B, and Claude Sonnet 4.5, under varied prompt engineering strategies and model sizes [\[RC3.J17\]](#)[\[RC3.J19\]](#);
- Execution of the evaluations in a free5GC and UERANSIM-based environment, using success rate, token consumption, and response time as the main assessment metrics [\[RC3.J17\]](#)[\[RC3.J19\]](#).

■ NEWTON — iN Edge netWork indusTrial automation

[WP id. Title]	Academic Team [Role: Name (Institution)]	Ericsson Team [Name (Research Area)]
NW2. Internet of Robotic Things (IoRT)	PI: Prof. Eric Rohmer (UNICAMP) PhD 1: Cesar Bastos (UNICAMP) MSc 1: Breno Portela (UNICAMP) MSc 2: Ervin Bolivar (UNICAMP)	Alberto Hata, Klaus Raizer (RA AI)
NW3. Distributed perception at the TROCA environment	PI: Ricardo Gudwin (UNICAMP) PhD 1: José Renato Borelli (UNICAMP)	Alberto Hata, Klaus Raizer (RA AI)
NW4. Programmable Data Plane	PI: Prof. Christian Rothenberg (UNICAMP) Co-PI: Prof. Fabio Verdi (UFSCar) Co-PI: Prof. Marcelo Luizelli (UNIPAMPA) Post-doc: Dr. Alireza Shirmarz (UFSCar) PhD 1: Francisco Vogt (UNICAMP) PhD 2: Arthur Simas (UNICAMP) MSc 1: Filipo Costa (UNICAMP) MSc 2: Victor H. S. Lopes (UNIPAMPA) MSc 3: Mateus N. de Bragatto (UFSCAR) UR: Gabriel Andrade (UFSCar)	Gergely Pongracz, Gyanesh Patra (RA Networks)

NW2: Internet of Robotic Things (IoRT)

NW2 focuses on the Internet of Robotic Things, targeting connected robotic systems that combine robotics, IoT, cloud computing, and intelligent orchestration to support heterogeneous, collaborative, and context-aware environments. While the original vision emphasized smart services and social applications, the WP has progressively evolved toward scalable architectures and industrially relevant use cases, where the integration of sensing, reasoning, and actuation must operate under realistic constraints. The main challenge is to build robotic ecosystems that can adapt to dynamic environments while coordinating human, robotic, and IoT agents in a coherent and efficient manner.

The research goal of this WP is to design and validate an adaptive IoRT architecture that supports context management, cognitive task planning, semantic perception, and multimodal interaction across heterogeneous agents. The adopted methodology combines middleware development, ontology-based knowledge representation, multimodal perception, LLM-assisted reasoning, robotic simulation, and prototype implementation. This approach supports the construction of a distributed and scalable ecosystem in which contextual data can be interpreted, shared, and used for higher-level decision-making and multi-agent coordination.

The main activities and achievements in this period can be summarized as follows:

- Progress in the development of a scalable IoRT architecture based on a bottom-up approach, extended toward more industrial and heterogeneous environments;

- Expansion of the Smart Hub architecture with a Smart Context Manager for real-time collection, interpretation, and management of contextual data from sensors and devices [RC3.C37].
- Introduction of a Dynamic Device Integrator to automate the integration of constrained IoT devices and improve system scalability;
- Development of a hybrid data management strategy combining relational persistence with flexible structures for real-time contextual information, together with ontology-based knowledge organization;
- Investigation of a cognitive architecture for multi-agent coordination, including task planning supported by LLMs and retrieval-augmented generation, as well as multimodal reasoning and distributed decision-making;
- Exploration of affective reasoning capabilities to support adaptive interaction based on user emotional states and interaction history;
- Advancement of semantic scene understanding for multi-agent robotics through open-vocabulary perception, SLAM, and Gaussian Splatting-based scene representation;
- Development of an algorithmic pipeline combining open-vocabulary segmentation, embedding generation, and ICP-based localization for semantic mapping with RGB, depth, and semantic rasterization support;
- Progress in the construction of the humanoid agent SAM, including redesign of actuator supports, prototyping of mechanical components, and validation of motion and structural stability;
- Refinement of sensor positioning, casing design, facial display integration, and gesture execution to improve the robot's interactive capabilities;
- Implementation of a multimodal perception setup with microphone array, pan-tilt control, and RGB-D vision to support human-robot interaction in noisy environments;
- Experiments with locally deployed LLMs for multimodal dialogue processing and emotional expression recognition, strengthening the robot's contextual awareness [RC3.C37];
- Validation of the proposed IoRT ecosystem through CoppeliaSim-based simulation, middleware integration, and early proof-of-concept experiments involving humans, robots, and IoT devices, including a use case using a learning-based framework for robotic feeding [RC3.C31];
- Two MSc defenses [RC3.H02][RC3.H03] that have continued their research contributions in the WP now as PhD students.

NW3: Distributed perception at the TROCA environment

TROCA³ was originally developed at UNICAMP in collaboration with Ericsson as a cognitive architecture for controlling transportation robots in a smart-factory simulation. Initial implementations relied on simplified assumptions, including homogeneous cognitive agents and privileged information (e.g., prior maps and precise coordinates).

The research goal of this WP is to evolve TROCA toward realistic scenarios by expanding perceptual capabilities and introducing distributed perception architecture where cognitive agents share local observations. The methodology assumes agents with limited sensing collaborating with a coordinating agent, supported by migration to modern execution environments.

The main activities and achievements in this period can be summarized as follows:

- Journal publication “An update on the MECA cognitive architecture” [RC3.A10]. This publication was developed as a follow up of the initial study on MECA by the PhD candidate José Renato Borelli, for this WP. There were unpublished advancements in the MECA Cognitive Architecture since its first journal publication, and the student took the role of

³ <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1016/j.cogsys.2019.09.011>

compiling the changes and organizing the material for this publication, producing an important reference for future MECA users.

- Migration of the TROCA environment to more recent software platforms, including ROS Noetic and the ongoing transition to ROS2, with the goal of enabling experiments under a modern middleware stack.
- Creation of a ROS2-based Docker environment and evaluation of Java-based communication alternatives, including ros2-java, rosbridge with jrosbridge, and pure Java clients such as jros2client and jros2services, resulted in successful prototype communication with ROS2 topics and services.
- Refactoring of TROCA components and related simulation code to adapt to ROS2 conventions, update the Aruco ROS node, and adjust CoppeliaSim scripts and ROS interfaces to the new API and naming conventions.
- Recomilation and integration of the simROS2 plugin, enabling the target factory simulation to operate with ROS2 and CoppeliaSim in the updated environment.
- Refactoring of TROCA and jsimulationmanager to support the newer Java JDK required by the ZeroMQ-based CoppeliaSim RemoteAPI replacement, culminating in successful execution of the TROCA environment in ROS2 and JDK 21.

NW4: Programmable Data Plane

The research goal of this WP carried over knowledge and team assets from NW1 through a reviewed research work plan to keep addressing open challenges posed by an evolving landscape of programmable targets, ranging from hardware embodiments like SmartNICs and programmable switches (Tofino) to various software stacks and AI accelerators. While P4 has enabled programmable packet processing, queue management has remained largely a fixed-function feature, with coarse-grained accounting and limited support for Active Queue Management (AQM) and scheduling policies. There is an open research challenge to understand the offloading options for network and user application functions across different targets and to evaluate the associated performance, cost, and energy trade-offs.

The WP focuses on evolving enabling research artifact tracks, including P7 for network emulation, PIPO-TG/P4 for traffic generation, and exploring SmartNIC (sNIC) Proof-of-Concept (PoC) experiments for offloading functions, including those running containerized environments. Furthermore, the WP explores emerging research areas such as the integration of neuromorphic computing chipsets and network-compute continuum architectures to empower next-generation programmable edge devices.

The main activities and achievements in this period can be summarized as follows:

- Hands-on engineering and technology knowledge-building efforts to establish the SMARTNESS Studio 5G (SS5G) infrastructure, incorporating new programmable hardware such as the NVIDIA BlueField-3 DPU (200GbE) into the research testbed;
- Mitigation of performance bottlenecks arising in virtualized environments through eBPF-based service mesh acceleration for cloud-native infrastructures [\[RC3.C06\]](#);
- In collaboration with the CL3 WP, top demo award at IEEE NetSoft for the work "Assessing QoE in Edge-Delivered Holographic Streaming with a Programmable Hardware Testbed" [\[RC3.C16\]](#), which featured a P7-based programmable testbed with edge computing slices;
- Ambitious tier-1 conference submissions:
 - "GhostQueues: Virtualizing Queue Semantics Beyond Hardware Limits" [\[RC3.J39\]](#), investigating programmable Traffic Manager abstractions, and
 - "GhostTwin: Enabling Live Network Digital Twin on Programmable Networks" [\[RC3.J40\]](#), plus one companion open-source tool demonstrator [\[RC3.J28\]](#);
- Research advancements around "the Offloading Dilemma" [\[RC3.C13\]](#) embodied in PoC implementations and experiments on offloading small language models (SLMs) to sNIC

- [\[RC3.J03\]](#) towards Network Agentic AI scenarios, exploring energy-efficient execution and acceleration on programmable targets; In-network collision avoidance logic inside P4 programmable hardware reducing response latency in conflict scenarios [\[RC3.C07\]](#);
- Continuous improvements of the P7 network emulation platform towards embracing digital twins, including support for Tofino 2, pipeline flexibility, native telemetry, partially demonstrated in ACM SIGCOMM 2025 (GhostTwin [\[RC3.C18\]](#) and SmartNet [\[RC3.C23\]](#)), bridging emulation performance and realism through programmable dataplanes;
 - Consolidation and feature improvements of Traffic Generation (TG) tools based on P4/Tofino programmable data planes:
 - P4DMA [\[RC3.C17\]](#), unlocking high-performance RDMA traffic generation;
 - Development of QU4C [\[RC3.J45\]](#), a novel P4-based strategy for high-fidelity reproduction of QUIC traffic on programmable switches;
 - P4Timely [\[RC3.C15\]](#), evaluating time synchronization resilience;
 - Advanced traffic generation methods featuring time-fidelity techniques framed as TFTG published last year in IEEE Network have evolved into new tool demos [\[RC3.J29\]](#) [\[RC3.J32\]](#);
 - Research developments on model-aware network testers for LLM workloads [\[RC3.C27\]](#) and adaptive queue scheduling via QueuePilot [\[RC3.C28\]](#);
 - Evaluation of novel OMNeT++ modules for 5G(r17)-TSN integration, delivering time synchronization and flow mapping, unsupported by other open-source simulators [\[RC3.C04\]](#).
 - RAN Disaggregation and Programmability through the FlexUP design [\[RC3.J06\]](#), focusing on CU-UP disaggregation to enhance 5G RAN performance shown in SIGCOMM25 [\[RC3.C19\]](#);
 - Development and evaluation of the Forro stream cipher in Tofino programmable hardware for remote attestation in data centers [\[RC3.A02\]](#)[\[RC3.D02\]](#);
 - Implementation and demonstration of the CRC4EVER proof-of-concept on P/Tofino switches, executing line rate routing and path verification through table-free CRC operations [\[RC3.C22\]](#).
 - Analysis of the impact of lightweight INT on the usage of ML for QoS prediction [\[RC3.J22\]](#);
 - Initiated competence building and technology exploration on neuromorphic computing paradigms in softwarized networks [\[RC3.C12\]](#);
 - A comprehensive survey of networking for A focused on LLM model workloads and their unique communication characteristics [\[RC3.J44\]](#);
 - Successful 12-month research abroad stay (BEPE) of PhD student Francisco Vogt at University of Amsterdam (UvA), collaborating with the EU SNS DESIRE6G project on Virtual Queues using the Per-Packet Value (PPV) concept, among other research tracks resulting in joint publications [\[RC3.C18\]](#), [\[RC3.C28\]](#), [\[RC3.C29\]](#) and submissions [\[RC3.J39\]](#), [\[RC3.J40\]](#).
 - Successful 6-month research abroad stay (BEPE) of MSc student Mateus Bragatto at Technische Universität Berlin (TU Berlin), including the opportunity to present a seminar on SDN, programmable devices, and an introduction to the P4 language for undergraduate students at TU Berlin, also collaborating with the project on Virtual Queues using the Per-Packet Value (PPV) concept, submission [\[RC3.J39\]](#).

■ C3LA — Cognitive Close Control Loops Architecture for Edge IoT

[WP id. Title]	Academic Team [Role: Name (Institution)]	Ericsson Team [Name (Research Area)]
CL3. Immersive Media	PI: Prof. Christian Rothenberg (UNICAMP) Co-PI: Prof. Vanessa Testoni (UNICAMP) Co-PI: Prof. Fabio Verdi (UFSCar) Post-doc: Alireza Shirmarz (UFSCar) PhD 1: Tariqul Islam (UNICAMP) PhD 2: Ariel Goes (UNICAMP) PhD 3: Alan Teixeira (UNICAMP) PhD 4: Públío Elon Correa da Silva (UFSCar)	Maria V. Marquezini (RA Networks) Harald Poblth, Lukasz Litwic (RA Digital Representation and Interaction)

<p>MSc 1: Rafael Clerici (UNICAMP) MSc 2: Emanuel Savegnago Maziero (UNICAMP) MSc 3: Gabriel Alves Baltazar (UNICAMP) UR: Carlos Marques (UFSCar)</p>
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CL3: Immersive Media

The third WP of the C3LA RS, namely CL3, is a direct evolution of the Holographic-Type Communications (HTC) research initiated in the CL2 spin-off, integrating assets from previous WPs (CL1, DM1, and DC1) that used XR/VR as a driving application. It addresses the challenge of transmitting holographic and volumetric media over next-generation networks under stringent throughput, latency, and quality constraints, with a particular focus on enabling immersive services that are beyond the capabilities of current 5G systems. The WP also explores how these media and their associated delivery pipelines can support the broader vision of the Internet of Senses.

The research goal of CL3 is to optimize end-to-end network and media delivery conditions so as to provide high QoE for volumetric video and related immersive content on head-mounted devices. The adopted methodology combines networked systems research, media compression and rendering experimentation, user-centered quality assessment, and testbed-based validation. It investigates AI-assisted compression approaches and emerging representations such as 3D Gaussian Splatting, light fields, and dynamic meshes, as well as transport and network-support mechanisms including L4S, slicing, and traffic shaping in order to assess their impact on multi-user immersive experiences.

The main activities and achievements in this period can be summarized as follows:

- Consolidation of expertise in XR, point-cloud video, and cloud gaming under a unified research line under a unified research strand, strengthening the collaboration between the involved teams and aligning the WP with the broader SMARTNESS strategy;
- Active participation in international standardization through team members registered as ISO/ITU-T SC29 WG7 (PEG) experts, participating in technical discussions on 3D Gaussian Splatting encoding, streaming, and quality assessment in scope of ISO/ITU-T SC29 and ITU-T SG21;
- Advancement of volumetric and 3D Gaussian Splatting research, including work on temporal consistency for GS datasets and Unity-based visualizer for dynamic streaming;
- Implementation of a Draco decoding benchmark in Unity to measure per-frame timing and processing performance for 3D content delivery and rendering workflows;
- Execution of subjective quality assessment studies on volumetric media streaming during two large-scale events at UNICAMP, with more than 30 participants, providing the basis for the development of a new quality metric using the testbed in [\[RC3.D03\]](#);
- Exploration of MPEG V-PCC as an additional compression alternative for point-cloud content, complementing the use of the Google Draco library in the WP's media pipeline;
- Adoption and integration of the 5G-MAG V3C immersive platform in Unity and deployment of a custom 5G USB dongle to enable Meta Quest 3 connectivity to a private 5G network of the SMARTNESS Studio 5G (SS5G), contributing to its inauguration of SMARTNESS through a demonstration (first in LATAM) of immersive media streaming over a private 5G network with USB-C tethering for HMD access and experimental validation;
- Investigation on the impact of channel metrics in 5G NSA and SA on video streaming QoE [\[RC3.C01\]](#), 360 video streaming [\[RC3.C30\]](#), and evaluation of bandwidth estimators and Impacts on real-time 360-video [\[RC3.J14\]](#);
- Study on mobile throughput forecasting for 5G using global tree-based models like LightGBM that offers the best balance of accuracy, robustness, and efficiency [\[RC3.C40\]](#);
- Development of ML-based methods to predict the operations and maintenance systems switchover towards proactive disaster recovery in 5G Networks [\[RC3.D12\]](#);

- Development and low-latency transport evaluation of the MATGen tool [[RC3.J04](#)] for realistic background traffic generation;
- Design and experimental evaluation of in-network LLM-based agents cost-feasible RTP video streaming optimization [[RC3.J20](#)];
- Rafael Pedrosa Clerici held his MSc qualification exam titled “A Programmable Environment for Assessment of Volumetric Media Transmission Quality”;
- Alan Teixeira da Silva completed his PhD qualification exam titled "Cross-Layer Volumetric Media Quality of Experience (QoE) Assessment in Immersive Virtual Reality”;
- Emanuel Savegnago Maziero started his MSc with a research line on immersive communication services, focusing on ML-based image and video compression;
- Gabriel Alves Baltazar also began his MSc with a research focus on new immersive media formats. These representations can be implemented through implicit methods, such as Neural Radiance Fields, or explicit techniques, like 3D Gaussian Splatting;
- Deepened research network through a 4-month research visit by MSc student Rafael Pedrosa Clerici to imec/UGent (Belgium) hosted by Prof. Filip de Turck and a 12-month BEPE FAPESP grant awarded to PhD candidate Tariq Islam to AAU (Austria) hosted by Prof. Christian Timmerer to advance volumetric media research tools and methodologies;
- Research collaboration with University of Catania on a Digital Twin (DT)-based Cloud Gaming framework designed to mitigate the effects of variable network conditions on video streaming and input responsiveness [[RC3.J05](#)];
- Research collaboration with Norwegian University of Science and Technology on Real-Time QoE-Aware RAN Control for 5G and Beyond [[RC3.J07](#)];
- Acceptance of the "MEI5GO" proposal to the Open RAN Brasil Call to develop and validate educational volumetric media applications using 5G Open RAN infrastructure.
- Scientific contributions in national and international events:
 - NetSoft 2025: Best Demo Award for "Assessing QoE in Edge-Delivered Holographic Streaming with a Programmable Hardware Testbed" [[RC3.C16](#)]
 - SBRC 2025: Presentation of "DCTPQ: Dynamic Cloud Gaming Traffic Prioritization Using Machine Learning and Multi-Queueing for QoE Enhancement" [[RC3.D04](#)]
 - SBRC 2025: Presentation of “Ambiente Programável para Transmissão e Análise de Qualidade de Experiência de Vídeo Volumétrico” [[RC3.D03](#)].
 - NetSoft 2025: Developed the CGReplay framework for capturing and replaying cloud gaming traffic for QoE assessment [[RC3.C14](#)]
 - NetSoft 2025: Development and experimental evaluation of in-network AR/CG traffic classification with RTP features and L4S integration [[RC3.C08](#)].
 - SIGCOMM 2025: Showcased the CGSynth cloud gaming synthesizer to address experimental reproducibility challenges [[RC3.C21](#)] that lead to a major cloud gaming QoE research submission to ACM TOMM [[RC3.J08](#)].
 - MSWiM 2025 Presentation of "Mobile 360° Video QoE: Measurement, Emulation, and GAN-Driven Throughput Synthesis" in Barcelona [[RC3.C30](#)]
 - NOMS 2025 paper: Investigation on the impact of channel metrics in 5G NSA and SA on Video Streaming QoE [[RC3.C01](#)]
 - NOMS 2026 short paper "Why Realistic Background Traffic Matters: Low-Latency Transport Evaluation with MATGen" [[RC3.J04](#)]
 - Milestone submission to the flagship ACM MM conference [[RC3.J47](#)] on VQUEST, a novel cross-layer measurement framework that presents an end-to-end pipeline spanning Draco-encoded point cloud delivery over QUIC, edge rendering on SMARTNESS Studio 5G private network, and subjective quality evaluation on a Meta Quest 3 HMD following ITU-T P.910 guidelines.

■ DEMIST — Distributed Edge Computing Swarm Intelligence

[WP id. Title]	Academic Team [Role: Name (Institution)]	Ericsson Team [Name (Research Area)]
DM2. Edge-assisted intelligent drone management	PI: Prof. Luiz Bittencourt (UNICAMP) Co-PI: Fernando von Zuben (UNICAMP) Co-PI: Fredrik Heintz (LiU) AR: Carlos Kamienski (UFABC) AR: Fabiola Oliveira (UFABC) AR: Francisco Airton Silva (UFPI) PhD 1: Mauricio Rodríguez (UNICAMP) PhD 2: Danielle Fortunato (UNICAMP) PhD3: Heictor Oliveira (UNICAMP) MSc: Lucas Soares (UNICAMP) UR: Ibini Santana (UNICAMP) UR: Lucas de Araújo (UNICAMP) UR: Felipe Capovilla (UNICAMP) UR: Rafaela Iwanow (UNICAMP)	Jean Martins (RA AI) Maria V. Marquezini (RA Networks)
DM3. Efficiency of Federated Learning for Telco Scenarios	PI: Luiz Bittencourt (UNICAMP) AR: Allan Souza (UNICAMP) AR Denis Rosário (UFPA) Dr. Carlos Senna (UNICAMP) MSc: Camilo H. Martins dos Santos (UNICAMP) MSc: Heitor Henrique da Silva (UNICAMP) MSc: Mateus Carmo de Oliveira (UNICAMP)	Klaus Raizer, Konstantinos Vandikas, Selim Ickin (RA AI) Maria V. Marquezini (RA Networks)

DM2: Edge-assisted intelligent drone management

This WP addresses open challenges towards the realization of intelligent aerial delivery in dense and dynamic urban environments, where multiple drones must navigate safely and efficiently alongside buildings, vehicles, weather disturbances, and other obstacles. DM2 focuses on reducing collision risk, improving trajectory planning, and enabling scalable drone management for last-mile logistics and related autonomous vehicle applications. Its scope also includes the broader challenge of coordinating entire fleets under realistic constraints on communication, energy, and infrastructure, with the goal of advancing methods that can be validated in realistic deployment settings.

Research goals of this WP include the development of collision-avoidance, autonomy, and coordination mechanisms for multi-drone delivery systems, integrated with edge/fog computing and 6G-oriented communication support. The adopted methodology combines simulation, network emulation, reinforcement learning, metaheuristics, and optimization-based modeling. This includes the design of distributed machine learning components at the edge, the analysis of control-aware energy efficiency, the formulation of bi-level logistics and truck–drone coordination models, the construction of OSM-grounded digital twins for signal-aware routing, and the exploration of dynamic system reasoning and adaptive metaheuristics for large-scale fleet operation.

The main activities and achievements in this period can be summarized as follows:

- A cooperative decentralized anti-collision algorithm, FACES, was modeled and implemented, then adapted to operate within the DREMS simulation scenario, establishing a foundation for safe multi-drone operation in shared airspace;
- Reinforcement learning approaches for collision avoidance were investigated in high-density drone delivery scenarios, including a training setup grounded in a Markov Decision Process formulation and evaluations that jointly account for edge-server load alongside flight safety [\[RC3.J25\]](#), [\[RC3.J48\]](#);

- The Edge4Drone paper [RC3.C09] at the INFOCOM NetRobotics workshop presented algorithmic contributions to managing landings and takeoffs in high-density distribution centers, addressing one of the most congested and risk-prone phases of urban drone delivery;
- A novel 4D single-agent planner, SFIPP-ST, was accepted for publication at AAMAS [RC3.J01], introducing safe flight interval path planning with soft and temporal constraints. The method natively handles heterogeneous UAV profiles with varying start times, speeds, and sizes, strictly enforces temporal no-fly zones, and models inter-agent conflicts through soft penalizing constraints;
- Research on energy-aware logistics and adaptive optimization advanced through a unified framework [RC3.J02] combining bi-level truck-drone routing co-optimized with power grid constraints, GPU-accelerated OSM-based 6G digital-twin path planning, and the refinement of the dopt-ARIA metaheuristic, validated on TSP, DTSP, and TTP benchmarks and complemented by a review of reinforcement learning methods for future hybrid integration;
- Dynamic drone fleet management through digital twin representations was explored, enabling real-time monitoring and control of individual drones within a shared virtual replica of the operational environment [RC3.J42];
- A systematic mapping of quantum computing techniques applied to UAV collision avoidance was conducted, contributing a structured overview of the field, an assessment of classical-quantum integration maturity, the identification of open challenges in the edge-cloud continuum, and a public compendium for reproducibility [RC3.J49];
- A systematic mapping study reviewed the literature on drone delivery services to analyze collision causes, prevention strategies, detour methods, and evaluation metrics, providing a taxonomy to improve operational safety and guide future research [RC3.J50];
- Relevant scientific contributions were published on collision recovery, energy efficiency, multi-agent self-distribution, and anti-collision modeling:
 - Performance evaluation of drone routes under collision and repair scenarios, assessing the operational cost of mid-flight failures and recovery strategies [RC3.D06];
 - Petri net-based modeling of drone deliveries, providing formal analysis of collision recovery sequences and energy consumption across delivery cycles [RC3.C32], [RC3.D06];
 - Multi-agent learning approaches for self-distributing stateful services across the computing continuum, with implications for distributed drone coordination logic [RC3.C03];
 - Best Paper Award at CBIC 2025 for a hybrid offline-online UAV path planning approach that combines precomputed optimal routes with dynamic in-flight adaptation to unforeseen events [RC3.D07];
 - Validation of fractional-order PID control for energy-efficient drone operation, demonstrating reduced power consumption in spraying missions [RC3.C33].
- Highlights of the UNetyEmu simulation platform released as open source⁴ include:
 - A SIGCOMM'25 demo [RC3.C20] presented an integrated framework for network emulation and multi-vehicle algorithm testing, incorporating drone-to-drone communication experiments for transmission and packet loss modeling, climate-aware extensions for wind and rain effects, and improved battery-consumption models covering takeoff, navigation, and landing phases;
 - A companion demonstration at SBRC [RC3.D01] showcased the same UNetyEmu platform in the Brazilian community, highlighting its open-source availability and applicability to realistic autonomous vehicle evaluation under communication and mobility constraints;

⁴ <https://github.com/smarness2030/UNetyEmu>

- Integration of ROS-2 with UNetyEmu, enabling topic exchange and sensor data extraction between the emulation environment and robotic middleware, completed with the UNetyEmuROS demonstrator for multi-vehicle simulation with full ROS2 sensor integration [[RC3.J41](#)].
- Strengthened collaboration with Linköping University, including two BEPE-supported research stays (MSc and PhD) with Prof. Fredrik Heintz's group to collaborate on drone management and collision avoidance, resulting in one joint publication [[RC3.J01](#)], and advances to the simulation framework with a decentralized cooperative reinforcement learning approach from the literature, including attention-based mechanisms for nearby-drone awareness.
- Initial collaboration with Prof. Xin-She Yang (Middlesex University London) on decentralized drone coordination in 6G environments using a hybrid swarm intelligence approach (e.g., Firefly-Bat), extending the single-drone 6G-aware planning toward multi-agent behavior.

DM3: Federated Learning for Telecom Scenarios

DM3 investigates distributed learning methods tailored to telecommunications scenarios where data and system heterogeneity limit generic Federated Learning (FL) approaches. The WP studies SplitFed Learning to address model privacy limitations of conventional FL.

The research goal is to adapt SplitFed Learning for telecom use cases and propose aggregation/client-selection mechanisms improving convergence and efficiency. The methodology includes testbed design comparing SplitFed with alternative paradigms under non-IID conditions.

The research objectives and expected results of this WP include:

- Improve learning dynamic heterogeneous distributed learning contexts, following the telecom scenarios requirements;
- Keep system performance within acceptable bounds;
- System heterogeneity (network and computing);
- Data/statistical heterogeneity (non-independent and identically distributed – non-IID).

The main activities and achievements in this period can be summarized as follows:

- Publication "The computing continuum: Past, present, and future" in Computer Science Review [[RC3.A09](#)] providing a RS-wide view on relevant research topics for the WP.
- An in-depth literature review was conducted that selected 116 articles addressing FL in telecom, contributed to two papers on the topic
 - Split Computing for Vehicle Detection in Smart Parking [[RC3.J37](#)]
 - Using LoRA for Continual Learning Scenarios in Split Learning [[RC3.J38](#)]
- Approval of three MSc qualifying exams;
- Initial testbed design (PPCL-Testbed) to support the WP activities and experiments;
- Publication on experimental framework for non-IID data in FL network telemetry [[RC3.J18](#)].
- Two infrastructure support projects were submitted: Distributed Intelligence Orchestration for Cloud Continuum Environments proposed for NVIDIA Robotics and Edge AI Call and to Amazon AWS (AWS Agentic AI call for proposals – Fall 2025).

■ ADVENTURE — Adaptive and Secure Network Applications over Industrial Internet

RS	WP# / Theme	Academic Team	Ericsson Team
ADVENTURE	AD1. Distributed Intelligence for Secure 6G Network Services	PI: Prof. Daniel Macêdo Batista (USP) Post-Doc: <i>tbd</i> (USP) PhD: Evgeni K. C. Ortega (USP) MSc: Ana Carla Quallio Rosa (USP) MSc: Lucas Seiki Oshiro (USP) UR: Giovanna Luísa Hirata dos Anjos (USP) UR: Ivan Gabriel Ferreira Dias (USP) UR: Renata Meyer Hobold (USP) UR: Thiago Duvanel Ferreira (USP)	Pedro G. (RA Networks)
	AD2. Blockchain-Based Governance	PI: Prof. Jó Ueyama (USP) Co-PI: Prof. Marco Amaral (UNICAMP) PhD 1: Rodrigo Dutra Garcia (USP)	Pedro Gomes (RA Networks)

AD1: Distributed Intelligence for Secure 6G Network Services

AD1 investigates distributed security mechanisms protecting 6G/B5G services against zero-day attacks using online/federated learning, NWDAF analytics, and privacy-preserving techniques across Internet and IoHT scenarios.

The research goal is to design adaptive, resilient intrusion detection architectures compatible with next-generation network constraints. The methodology combines reproducible environments, traffic datasets, and explainability analysis.

The main activities and achievements in this period can be summarized as follows:

- Development of an IDS to protect a simulated Internet of Health Things (IoHT) environment, connected in a 5G network, integrating federated learning and NWDAF [RC3.J34]. This IDS and all the code to reproduce the simulated environment are available as free and open-source software on GitHub⁵.
- Experimental environment for conducting Online Federated Learning, available as free and open-source software⁶, showcasing differential privacy with explainability.
- Investigation showing 22% data reduction via LIME/SHAP feature pruning using real-world traffic captured from multiple devices on a network to feed an IDS⁷. Research artifacts are available as open-source⁸.
- DNS malicious flow IDS with SHAP analysis⁹ revealing public dataset weaknesses [RC3.J35].
- MSc defense [RC3.H01] produced an NS-3 smart-grid module for GOOSE/SV protocols available as open-source¹⁰, to generate smart grid traffic (based on GOOSE and SV protocols) and evaluate how B5G networks can meet strict QoS requirements [RC3.J33].

⁵ <https://github.com/edusporto/fl-nwdaf-ioht>

⁶ <https://github.com/Renatata-H/online-federated-learning>

⁷ https://github.com/th-duvanel/ids-explainability/blob/main/tese/Thiago_Duvanel_Ferreira_TCC.pdf

⁸ <https://github.com/th-duvanel/ids-explainability>

⁹ <https://github.com/giovannahirata/IDS-DNS>

¹⁰ <https://github.com/lucasoshiro/GridGooseSV>

AD2: Blockchain-based governance mechanisms

AD2 investigates decentralized governance for B5G/6G preserving privacy while enabling transparent QoE assessment. The WP addresses centralized ML limitations through blockchain coordination and privacy-preserving learning.

The research goal is to design architectures combining blockchain with TFHE-based computation and verifiable mechanisms for distributed validation. The methodology includes literature analysis and proof-of-concept implementation.

The main activities and achievements in this period can be summarized as follows:

- Systematic literature review on privacy-preserving QoE techniques [RC3.A04].
- TFHE-based QoE architecture with proof-of-concept implementation [RC3.A01].
- Research progress by PhD student Rodrigo Dutra Garcia with BEPE at University of Southern California (USC), USA.

■ NEXT — Research Strand for Work Package Incubation

This new RS serves as an organizational thrust, effectively acting as a “WP Incubator”, curating emerging technology scouting and competence building to feed updated research plans of existing WPs or to consolidate into the formation of new WPs or even new core SMARTNESS RS.

This flexible structure targets strategic gaps in the state-of-the-art such as post-quantum cryptography, quantum networking, optics/metasurfaces, Generative AI research and technologies (e.g. LLM). The main areas of activities can be clustered as follows.

Quantum Networking/Computing and Security: [RC3.A07] introduces QuantumNetSec applying quantum ML to network security detection; [RC3.D05] introduces the Semi-Supervised Quantum Generative Adversarial Network (sQGAN) for attack detection, which integrates semi-supervised learning with quantum adversarial architectures; [RC3.D11] proposes Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) in software-defined QKD networks to secure Open RAN architectures; [RC3.D08] investigates Black Hole Repeater attacks, highlighting the urgent need for adaptive monitoring solutions and resilient architectures to secure quantum networks; [RC3.D10] investigates security vulnerabilities in quantum entanglement networks arising from the reliance on trusted repeaters; [RC3.A03][RC3.C11] advance two-stage Q-learning routing in entanglement networks; [RC3.C36] introduces Q-CAST Mobility, an adaptation of the Q-CAST quantum routing protocol, specifically optimized for mobile quantum nodes; [RC3.D09] proposes a dynamic scheduling strategy for quantum networks that optimizes resource efficiency by adjusting purification rounds and reusing idle EPR pairs; [RC3.C35] explores Blind Quantum Computation (BQC) frameworks augmented with Quantum Machine Learning (QML) by implementing a network of entangled clients and a quantum server. [RC3.D14] provides initial post-quantum crypto results for the replacement of optimized conventional schemes while maintaining 5G/6G latency requirements.

GenAI and LLM technologies: [RC3.C05] studies the use of lightweight LLMs in scope of 3GPP specifications; [RC3.D13] analyzes smart contract generation Using LLMs; [RC3.J43] benchmarks LLM agents (OperAID) for autonomous Kubernetes fault remediation. These works will be considered for inclusion in ongoing WPs that already leverage LLMs (e.g. DC1, DC4, NW2, NW4, CL3) or eventually the foundation for a new GenAI / Fundamental AI WP.

HW/Optical & Metasurfaces: [RC3.C38] investigates methods based on unsupervised learning for pinpointing faulty optical amplifiers; [RC3.C34] reports nonuniform surfaces and structural anisotropy as promising candidates for investigating advanced light-matter interactions and for integration into next-generation photonic platforms; [RC3.A05] demonstrates electrically tunable silicon-organic

metasurfaces as WDM demultiplexers; [RC3.A06] validates nanofabrication of all-dielectric metasurfaces via pulsed thermal scanning probe lithography; [RC3.A08] explores surface lattice resonances in gold nanoparticle arrays for high-performance sensing.

Testbed Innovation: [RC3.J27] proposes an automated testing framework for RESTful APIs that generates test cases directly from YANG specifications; [RC3.C26] investigates a prototype based on low-power wide-area networks (LPWANs) and SDN programmable data planes with PDPs that could open the doors to mitigate digital exclusion in technologically underserved populations; [RC3.J26] presents Mininet-X as a unified emulator for satellite and aeronautical ad hoc networks; [RC3.J36] develops a digital twin framework for hybrid IEEE 802.15.4 experimentation, leveraging an extension of Wmediumd [RC3.C25], bridging simulation-physical experiments as pursued in the SMARTNESS Studio 5G (SS5G). The infrastructure upgrades will be discussed in the next Section [II.D](#).

Further activities within the NEXT RS include the analysis of knowledge dynamics through a systematic mapping and global assessments of how 5G/6G [RC3.J09] and XR [RC3.J10] technologies are being developed and diffused across specific vertical sectors such as Smart Grids [RC3.J11]. This "research on research" approach serves to identify strategic gaps and knowledge flows between academia and industry, directly supporting the center's Technology Transfer and innovation management objectives. By examining these innovation systems globally and within the Brazilian context, these activities provide the empirical evidence needed to steer potential long-term research plans and ensure alignment with emerging technological trends.

Altogether, during Y3, efforts embodied within the NEXT RS have delivered 10+ publications across different strategic areas and the effective formation of one WP described in the following.

AI1: Audio Semantic Communication in Heterogeneous Networks

This newly incubated WP was motivated by the Fundamental AI research track at Ericsson to explore semantic communication paradigms for 6G audio transmission, where traditional Shannon-capacity limits are replaced by task-relevant information extraction to reduce bandwidth while preserving meaning.

Future wireless networks must support massive IoT connectivity and intelligent edge services under heterogeneous computational constraints, raising key questions: How can autoencoders extract compact semantic audio features for efficient transmission? Can federated learning across diverse edge devices optimize these representations without raw data sharing? What encoder-decoder pairing strategies enable interoperability between nodes with varying computational/energy capabilities while maintaining reconstruction quality, low latency, and bandwidth efficiency?

Objectives of AI1 include: Develop autoencoder architectures (e.g., leveraging wav2vec 2.0, Whisper) for semantic audio feature extraction; validate federated vs. centralized learning with optimal rounds/epochs; design adaptive encoders/decoders for heterogeneous nodes; model heterogeneous transmission networks; implement communication protocols for compact semantic representations; evaluate via reconstruction quality, latency, bandwidth savings, and computational cost metrics.

Key achievements so far include: Literature review established theoretical foundations (wav2vec 1.0/2.0, Whisper, wav2vec-vec2wav); implemented/evaluated wav2vec-vec2wav baseline in ideal channels; Ricardo Guimarães Leite optimized federated learning (rounds/epochs compromise, qual exam Aug/2025); Marcos Ferreira Semolini advanced centralized training with pre-trained encoders (wav2vec, Whisper), VQ/PQ compression, large-scale dataset validation, and initial heterogeneous encoder-decoder experiments; Infrastructure upgrades: new high-performance lab machine supports experimental workload.

D. Lab Infrastructures

■ SMARTNESS Studio 5G (SS5G)

The SMARTNESS Studio 5G (SS5G), located within the LEMAC facilities at FEEC-UNICAMP, represents a major infrastructure milestone for the Center's research, technology transfer, and demonstration capabilities. Officially inaugurated on December 3, 2025, the laboratory underwent extensive renovations throughout 2025, funded by SMARTNESS resources and a R\$150,000 grant from UNICAMP's CALL PRP 003/2024 Infrastructure Support Subprogram.

Widely publicized across various media outlets, the inauguration of the SS5G marked a significant milestone for Unicamp, Ericsson, and the Brazilian technological landscape as a whole. Presided over by Prof. Dr. Christian Rothenberg, Director of SMARTNESS 2030, the event was attended by senior administration representatives from UNICAMP, Ericsson, and FAPESP, as well as public officials and leading companies in the communications sector.

The SS5G will be fundamental not only for supporting research activities but also for the pre-compliance assessment processes of products and services. Its aim is to accelerate and improve the technical suitability of research results for Technology Transfer (TT) processes, given that product and Service Certification plays a crucial role in managing TT in Brazil by helping to ensure the quality, safety, and compliance of developed and marketed products and services.

Official Launch of the SS5G on 3 December 2025.

The SS5G features a fully renovated research environment with redesigned electrical installations, air conditioning, dedicated data networking, and ergonomic furniture. It hosts an Ericsson Private 5G Standalone (SA) network with a base station and strategically distributed Radio Dots providing comprehensive coverage across the FEEC building. This infrastructure supports low-latency, high-reliability connectivity for multiple simultaneous devices, enabling advanced experimentation.

The laboratory serves multiple strategic functions:

- Research validation: End-to-end testing of Work Packages including XR streaming (CL3), edge offloading (DC WPs), drone management (DM2), and immersive media applications.
- Technology transfer: Pre-compliance assessment and product validation for industry partners.
- Education and demonstration: Hosting demos, workshops, and technology showcases for academic and industry audiences.
- Inter-institutional collaboration: Open access for partner institutions and technology companies.

Post-Renovation Laboratory Facilities coined “SMARTNESS Studio 5G (SS5G)”

The private 5G SA network comprises:

- Router (1 RU): Connecting Basebands, Servers and external networks
- Baseband 5G (1 RU) - Interfacing 5G Antennas and the EPC
- Indoor Radio Unit (2 RU) - Cabled to four indoor antennas and connected to the 5G Baseband
- Server for EPC (1 RU) - Hosting the Evolved Packet Core
- Server for Applications (1 RU) - Hosting on supporting services and applications
- Power 48V DC Supply (1 RU)

The private 5G base station was installed in the SS5G lab, and wireless access points (“DOTS”) were distributed throughout the FEEC building. The goal is for these points to be used by the entire academic community for research, development, demonstrations, or other relevant use cases. The distribution of the radio dots was planned to ensure comprehensive coverage in strategic areas of the FEEC building. These access points connect to the baseband unit, allowing the private 5G network to support multiple simultaneous devices with low latency.

Radio Dot Distribution throughout the FEEC/Unicamp building

With indoor 5G SA, our connectivity will be unique for carrying out an experimental evaluation of use cases of the WPs, featuring Proof of Concepts including XR devices, SmartNICs, and servers, altogether enhancing the technological and research capabilities for Y4.

The 5G private network represents a milestone towards the SMARTNESS vision of a multi-site testbed based on interconnected experimental facilities deployed at the partner institutions in order to support several application scenarios, as illustrated in Figure 6.

SMARTNESS testbed approach and selected technologies for cutting-edge research

Target experiments include (1) drone control and VR experiences managed via 5G-enabler modules, (2) smart grid monitoring via smart power meters, and (3) demos of vehicular networks with radio-controlled miniature model cars, Raspberry Pi, and Arduino boards. The processing of the data generated by the applications can be done in a computer powered with a GPU (4) emulating the edge of the network. When this processing is not needed, the data produced will be accessed directly from the application scenarios (5). At the top of the figure is presented the main connection and decision infrastructure of the island: P4-compatible switches (6) connected to a server featuring a SmartNIC (7) providing core network emulation capabilities. The existing infrastructure (8) of each institution will also be integrated into each SMARTNESS island via P4 programmables switches.

■ SS5G Task Force (SS5GTF)

With the implementation of the SS5GTF, SMARTNESS activities now benefit from a powerful initiative aimed at accelerating and intensifying the center's TT processes. To this end, the SS5G Task Force (SS5GTF) was set to build competence and coordinate laboratory utilization and research alignment through weekly Thursday meetings focused on strategic planning, WP integration, technical presentations, and technology transfer monitoring. All discussions and decisions are documented in a dedicated Google Drive repository accessible to Center members.

The task force ensures:

- Rigorous activity monitoring and market alignment;
- Identification of technology transfer opportunities;
- Compliance with regulations and ethical standards;
- Integration of laboratory capabilities across research strands.

SS5GTF meeting

SMARTNESS Studio 5G T... ▾

Gerenciar participantes

Tipo ▾ Pessoas ▾ Modificado ▾ Fonte ▾

Nome ↑	Data da modificação	Tamanho do	Classificado
0.DOCS - Official-Documentation-Ericsson-5G-SA-Indoor	4 de dez. de 2025 Christian Este	—	⋮
Ericsson 5G Open Innovation Center - Indaiatuba	23 de out. de 2025 Christian Est	—	⋮
Fotos-Videos	31 de out. de 2025 Christian Estr	—	⋮
Meetings	23 de out. de 2025 Christian Est	—	⋮
SOTA-Related-Work-References	4 de dez. de 2025 Christian Este	—	⋮
Standards	31 de out. de 2025 eu	—	⋮
Troubleshooting-Operations-Etc	2 de dez. de 2025 Christian Este	—	⋮
0100102290-Unicamp_Smartness_EP5G_VC02-final.pdf	23 de out. de 2025 Christian Est	5,4 MB	⋮
Smartness Studio 5G - floor plan	5 de fev. arthur simas	86 KB	⋮

SS5GTF Google Drive

■ SMARTNESS - LEMAC Facilities

The main SMARTNESS laboratory at LEMAC (Laboratory of Applied and Computational Electromagnetics) is undergoing expansion to accommodate advanced testbed infrastructure. Key upgrades include the following:

- Integration of a fully anechoic chamber supporting measurements up to 18 GHz
- Installation of a Vector Network Analyzer (VNA) for measurements up to 500 GHz (collaboration with ALTAVE, FAPESP EMU process # 2022/11596-0)
- Consolidation of LEMAC 1 and LEMAC 2 spaces adjacent to the existing LCA laboratory

The combined SS5G and LEMAC facilities position SMARTNESS as Brazil's leading experimental environment for next-generation network research, supporting the full technology development lifecycle from algorithm design through pre-commercial validation.

■ Projects and Collaborations fueled by SS5G

Building on the capabilities described above, SS5G expands the Center's capacity to support new experimental activities aligned with SMARTNESS. In particular, the infrastructure creates conditions for the development of application-aware telemetry capable of measuring network behavior and informing service-driven traffic management, with a future integration path for open, disaggregated, components (e.g. Open5GS, Free5GC) and open APIs (e.g. CAMARA).

The private 5G SA environment also supports controlled studies on energy consumption and sustainability under different usage profiles (as pursued by the TRU STA and FAPESP CPTen # 2021/11380-5), as well as latency-sensitive evaluations involving mobile multimedia QoE, volumetric and immersive media (as pursued by the CL3 WP, see for example [RC3.J47]). These directions are consistent with the laboratory's role in end-to-end validation, multi-device experimentation, and 5G-and-beyond use cases.

The infrastructure also strengthens direct collaborations already associated with the Center. A relevant case is collaboration with one recent FAPESP project (process # 2025/05448-7) coordinated by Prof. Dalton Soares Arantes on hardware-accelerated complex-valued neural networks for next-generation wireless communications, for which SS5G may provide a controlled environment for over-the-air validation in MIMO, massive MIMO, and beamforming scenarios. In the same direction, the linked postdoctoral project (process # 2025/11548-4) on advanced MIMO integration and AI-based RAN orchestration is expected to consolidate a 5G + FPGA experimental platform connecting physical-layer processing, near-real-time orchestration, and slice-aware operation.

SS5G also provides renewed validation opportunities for the longstanding FAPESP thematic project PORVIR-5G collaboration (process # 2020/05182-3), particularly in studies involving programmability, orchestration, virtualization, QoE-aware slicing, URLLC-oriented communication for drones, and immersive 5G services.

Finally, SS5G will be used for baseline experiments of 5G transmissions of point cloud video for educational purposes as proposed by the recently approved MEI5GO project, coordinated by Kleber Vieira from UFG, with key participation from CL3 WP and IC/Unicamp lab coordinated by Prof. Carlos Trujillo, was officially selected as one of the applications for Phase 3 of the OpenRAN@Brasil program to explore immersive educational experiences through metaverse and volumetric video technologies.¹¹

E. Education and Dissemination of Knowledge (EDK)

The activities carried out within the scope of Education and Dissemination of Knowledge (EDK), referring to the third year of operation of the Center, are described in EDK Report #03 (REDK3). As established in the approved plan, the actions were organized into seven strategic dimensions: Internal Communication and Endomarketing; Offline Media and Press Relations; Social Media and Online Communication; Scientific Events; Teaching; Specialized Publications; and Human Capital Management. For each of these dimensions, performance indicators, annual targets, and corresponding documentary evidence mechanisms were established, enabling systematic monitoring of activities and analysis of the results achieved during the period.

Within the scope of Internal Communication and Endomarketing, actions focused on consolidating internal information flows, standardizing institutional materials, and strengthening the Center's visual identity. With regard to Offline Media and Press Relations, activities included engagement with media outlets, preparation of press releases, and dissemination of results through institutional communication channels.

In Social Media and Online Communication, the Center's digital presence was maintained through regular updates on the institutional website and social media platforms. Regarding scientific events, the Center organized and participated in relevant national and international conferences in the field, including NOMS, NetSoft, and SBRC.

In the Teaching dimension, the scientific and technological results of the project contributed to curriculum updates and to the qualified training of the Center's human resources. With respect to Specialized Publications, the strategy of prioritizing journals and conferences of recognized impact in the field was maintained.

Finally, within the Human Capital Management dimension, activities included the training and supervision of undergraduate research students, Master's, Ph.D., and postdoctoral researchers, as well as initiatives aimed at recruitment and researcher qualification.

¹¹ <https://openranbrasil.org.br/openranbrasil-avanca-para-fase-de-aplicacoes-e-realiza-workshop-presencial-da-fase-3/>

For the subsequent period, the continuation of the structured actions across the seven strategic dimensions is foreseen, with emphasis on expanding international engagement, strengthening extension activities, and maintaining high-impact scientific production, in accordance with the goals established in the approved work plan.

F. Technology Transfer (TT)

The third year of Technology Transfer activities at CPE SMARTNESS 2030 was characterized by an extensive array of technical initiatives, site visits, meetings, and efforts focused on technological knowledge transfer and international standardization.

The management of the Technology Transfer area was led by Dr. Eduardo Sartori, a postdoctoral fellow under the Research Management Postdoctoral Fellowship Program (PPDG) for Large Thematic Research Centers, funded by the Office of the Vice-Rector for Research at UNICAMP. With a focus on meta-research, the initiative aimed to advance “research on research” within three key areas: Executive Management, Technology Transfer & Innovation, and Education & Knowledge Dissemination.

As an ambitious and groundbreaking initiative, the program aims to enhance Research Management by applying rigorous scientific methodologies. It aspires to leave a lasting impact, sharing its expertise with UNICAMP and the broader national research community.

Key Technology Transfer activities included the final implementation and launch of the SS5G Laboratory (SMARTNESS STUDIO 5G). This project was a major focus during 2025, fulfilling one of the core goals established in Dr. Eduardo Sartori’s original Work Plan. Affiliated with LEMAC (Laboratory of Applied and Computational Electromagnetics), the SS5G laboratory stands as one of Brazil’s premier facilities for 5G R&D, offering a secure and highly sophisticated technological environment that remains accessible to anyone looking to innovate in the industry.

Strategic highlights of the year include new partnerships with ANATEL and ETSI focused on standardization and knowledge sharing. These joint efforts aim to refine 5G regulations and develop future 6G standards. These initiatives, as well as all subsequent activities, will be detailed in the RTT3 report.

G. Management, Structure and Governance Plan (GEO)

A comprehensive and detailed examination of SMARTNESS Management, Structure, and Governance (GEO) initiatives is provided in the GEO yearly Report #03 (RGEO3). This report meticulously outlines essential concepts and empirical evidence, serving to underscore the achievements attained through the implementation of GEO action plan, including:

- **Organization:** This encompasses our overarching management structure, featuring an Executive Committee (EC), a Scientific & Technology Advancements Board (STAB) divided into Research Strands (RS) and Scientific & Technology Areas (STA), support from Ericsson Research (ER), and input from the International Advisory Board (IAB).
- **Quality Assurance and Risk Management:** This involves reviewing processes and data management protocols adhering to FAIR data principles and practices for risk management.
- **Communication Tools:** This entails the adoption of social network platforms, data repositories, and mailing lists to facilitate effective communication.

- **Administrative Procedures and Workflows:** This includes protocols for news and knowledge dissemination, content publication, evaluation and approval of Work Packages, submission of publications, and scheduling of regular technical and administrative meetings.
- **Periodic Reports:** This pertains to reports addressing management, technical, and financial aspects of SMARTNESS 2030 ERC, providing periodic insights into project dimensions.

III. Institutional Support

After the third year of activities, we can report that all the required institutional support is still being provided on various fronts, serving as key support for achieving the Center's objectives efficiently and effectively. Among institutional support actions in Y3, we can highlight:

UNICAMP Research Pro-Rectorate (PRP). The Grant Office (GO) affiliated with UNICAMP's PRP is designed to provide institutional support to researchers by reducing the administrative tasks inherent in conducting research. Through Resolution CEPE-A-001/2024, on 06/02/2024, the Support Program for the Management of Large Thematic Research Centers¹² was created, under the coordination of the Dean of Research, which aims to complement the operating infrastructure of large-scale projects. The Program is made up of three support subprograms:

1. **Postdoctoral Scholarship Subprogram in Research Management (PPDG)** aims to meet the needs of large thematic centers with three modalities: Education Management and Knowledge Diffusion (EKD), Technology Transfer and Innovation (TTI) Management, and Executive Project Management (EPM).
2. **Higher Level Technical Support Subprogram (ProATS)** aims to meet the needs of higher education professionals to work and operate equipment installed in large research centers.
3. **Infrastructure Support Subprogram (InfraPeq)** aims to finance the recovery or improvement of existing facilities, as well as adaptations to spaces to meet new demands at two research centers.

The SMARTNESS 2030 ERC has received significant support from UNICAMP PRP:

- **Full support to the Management team through three PPDG grants.** During Y3, the SMARTNESS 2030 ERC has all three management positions supported through UNICAMP PPD: Dr. Eduardo José Sartori is the current Technology Transfer (TT) Manager, Dr. Roberta Steganhá, the Education and Knowledge Dissemination (EDK) Manager and Dr. Bárbara Ilze Semensato, the Executive Project (EP) Manager. More details can be found in the companion reports, namely, RTT3, REDK3, and RGEO3.
- **Lab reform additional support through "InfraPeq."** An award of R\$ 150,000.00 was used for complementary renovation expenses of the new 5G laboratory facilities (SMARTNESS Studio 5G) located at LEMAC/FEEC/UNICAMP.

FEEC Institutional Support Office for Researchers EAIP (*Escritório de Apoio Institucional ao Pesquisador*, in Portuguese) of FEEC/UNICAMP has supported SMARTNESS 2030 ERC in all the requested aspects (e.g. semesterly financial reports, acquisitions, etc.).

FEEC Institutional Communication Secretariat (SCI): Provide support in building communication strategies with the internal and external community of FEEC, assisting in the dissemination of the faculty's results and safeguarding its visual identity and public relations. SMARTNESS 2030 ERC has been using SCI's services and support for communication with society, whether in interaction with the press or in the preparation and dissemination of news.

¹² <https://prp.unicamp.br/en/grandes-centros/programa-de-apoio/>

UNICAMP Innovation Agency (INOVA): SMARTNESS 2030 ERC relies on guidance and improvement on IPR practices through close collaboration with INOVA.

UNICAMP Development Foundation (FUNCAMP) administrative services have provided all the necessary expertise for successful project management support, aiding UNICAMP as the host institution in managing the financial resources and assets contributed by ERICSSON financially.

We conclude by thanking UNICAMP for all resources and efforts to support the needs related to research management, administration, and physical space of SMARTNESS 2030 ERC, contributing to the evident competence and excellence of its research and development activities.

IV. List of Publications

All publications include their DOI links and are publicly available through the SMARTNESS publications website (<https://smartness2030.tech/publications/>) and the Zenodo community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/smartness2030/>).

A) Papers in indexed scientific periodicals

- RC3.A01** Rodrigo Dutra Garcia, Gowri Ramachandran, Christian Esteve Rothenberg, Daniel Macêdo Batista, Jó Ueyama. **“Towards a Decentralized and Privacy-Preserving Quality of Experience System for 6G Networks”**. In Distributed Ledger Technologies: Research and Practice, EDITION, 38(2), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3772072>.
- RC3.A02** Rodrigo Alexander de Andrade Pierini, Caio Teixeira, Christian Rodolfo Esteve Rothenberg e Marco Aurélio Amaral Henriques. **“Implementation and evaluation of the Forro stream cipher in Tofino programmable hardware for remote attestation in datacenters”**. In Journal of the Brazilian Computer Society, 2026. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5753/jbcs.2026.5625>.
- RC3.A03** Diego Abreu, Arthur Pimentel, David Moura, Christian Rothenberg, Antônio Abelém. **“A for quantum two-stage Q-learning routing approach entanglement networks”**. In Annals of Telecommunications, 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12243-025-01090-4>.
- RC3.A04** Rodrigo Dutra Garcia, Gowri Sankar Ramachandran, Christian Esteve Rothenberg, Bhaskar Krishnamachari, Jó Ueyama. **“A survey of in privacy-preserving mechanisms on quality of experience next-generation networks”**. In Computer Networks, 2026. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comnet.2025.111899>.
- RC3.A05** Ruth E. Rubio-Noriega, Franck D. Soria-Pinedo, Mark Clemente-Arenas, Julio V. Urbina, Hugo Enrique Hernandez-Figueroa, Akhlesh Lakhtakia. **“Electrically for tunable wavelength-division multiplexing systems”**. In Optical Engineering, 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1117/1.OE.64.7.077103>.
- RC3.A06** Paloma E. S. Pellegrini, Luana De-Moraes, Freddy Jara Poma, Silvia Vaz Guerra Nista, Frederico H. Cioldin, Hugo Enrique Hernández-Figueroa, Stanislav Moshkalev. **“Nanofabrication of all-dielectric metasurfaces through pulsed thermal scanning probe lithography”**. In Scientific Reports, 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-07428-1>.
- RC3.A07** Diego Abreu, David Moura, Christian Esteve Rothenberg, Antônio Abelém. **“QuantumNetSec: Quantum Machine Learning for Network Security”**. In International Network Management, Journal 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/nem.70018>.
- RC3.A08** Ursula F. S. Roggero, Carlos J. Rojas-Bejarano, César A. Herreño-Fierro, Andreas Seifert, Aitzol Garcia-Etxarri, Hugo E. Hernández-Figueroa, Mario Zapata-Herrera. **“Surface lattice resonances for high-performance sensing: study on gold nanoparticle arrays”**. In Optics Express, 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1364/OE.564444>.
- RC3.A09** Luiz F. Bittencourt, Roberto Rodrigues-Filho, Josef Spillner, Filip De Turck, José Santos, Nelson L.S. da Fonseca, Omer Rana, Manish Parashar, Ian Foster. **“The computing continuum: Past, present, and future”**, 2025. In Computer Science Review. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosrev.2025.100782>.
- RC3.A10** José Renato Borelli, Ricardo Ribeiro Gudwin. **“An update on the MECA cognitive architecture”**. In Journal of Ningbo University Natural Science & Engineering DOI: <https://doi.org/10.20098/j.cnki.1001-5132.2025.0105>.

B) Papers in non-indexed scientific periodicals

C) Papers presented at international conferences

- RC3.C01** Raza Ul Mustafa; Md Tariqul Islam; Christian Esteve Rothenberg. **"Investigating the Impact of Channel Metrics in 5G NSA and SA on Video Streaming QoE"**, In IEEE Network Operations and Management Symposium (NOMS), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/NOMS57970.2025.11073587>.
- RC3.C02** Guilherme Mendes Vieira de Matos, Washington Rodrigo Dias da Silva, Fábio Luciano Verdi, Andrew Williams. **"DECOMPOSER: Functional decomposition and distributed execution of monolithic applications to heterogeneous resources"**. In IEEE Network Operations and Management Symposium (NOMS), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/NOMS57970.2025.11073700>.
- RC3.C03** Bernardo Pandolfi Costa, Heitor Henrique da Silva, Analucia S. Morales, Luiz F. Bittencourt, Alison R. Panisson, Roberto Rodrigues-Filho. **"A Multi-agent Approach to Self-distributing Systems"**. In Barolli, L. (eds) Advanced Information Networking and Applications (AINA). Lecture Notes on Data Engineering and Communications Technologies, 2025. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-87766-7_12.
- RC3.C04** Sergio Rossi Brito Da Silva, Francisco Germano Vogt, Fabricio Rodriguez Cesen, Marcelo Caggiani Luizelli, Christian Esteve Rothenberg, Gyanesh Patra. **"Bridging TSN and 5G: Synchronization and Flow Mapping for Smart International Conference on Network Manufacturing"**. In IEEE 11th International Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/NetSoft64993.2025.11080615>.
- RC3.C05** José De Arimatéa Passos Lopes Júnior, Jayr Pereira, Diedre Santos Do Carmo, Roberto Lotufo, Christian Esteve Rothenberg. **"Lightweight LLMs for 3GPP Specifications: Fine-Tuning, Retrieval-Augmented Generation and Quantization"**. In IEEE 11th International Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/NetSoft64993.2025.11080581>.
- RC3.C06** Arthur J Simas, Christian Esteve Rothenberg, Gergely Pongrácz. **"eSeMeshA: eBPF-based Service Mesh Acceleration for Cloud-Native Infrastructures"**. In IEEE 11th International Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/NetSoft64993.2025.11080556>.
- RC3.C07** Fabricio E Rodriguez Cesen, Francisco Germano Vogt, Marcelo Caggiani Luizelli, Christian Esteve Rothenberg, Géza Szabó. **"Harnessing P4 for In-Network Unmanned Aerial Vehicle Collision Avoidance"**. In IEEE 11th International Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/NetSoft64993.2025.11080564>.
- RC3.C08** Alireza Shirmarz, Mateus N. Bragatto, Fábio Luciano Verdi, Suneet Kumar Singh, Christian E. Rothenberg, Gyanesh Patra. **"In-Network AR/CG Traffic Classification Entirely Deployed in the Programmable Data Plane: Unlocking RTP Features and L4S Integration"**. In IEEE 11th International Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/NetSoft64993.2025.11080610>.
- RC3.C09** Lucas de Paula Soares, Fabíola Martins Campos de Oliveira, Carlos A. Kamienski, Luiz F. Bittencourt. **"Edge4Drone: Managing Landings and Takeoffs in High-Density Distribution Centers"**. In The 18th International Workshop on Networked Robotics and Communication Systems (NetRobiCS 2025, ex WiSARN), organized in conjunction with IEEE Conference on Computer Communications Workshops (INFOCOM WKSHPS), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/INFOCOMWKSHPS65812.2025.11152762>.

- RC3.C10** Gabriel Espindola, Matheus Pires, Gustavo Spadotto, Cristiano Both, Bruno Silvestre, Kleber Cardoso, Andrew Williams, Fabio Verdi, Sand Correa. **“Demonstrating the Advantages of Computational Offloading of XR Services via WebAssembly”**. In IEEE/IFIP Network Operations and Management Symposium (NOMS), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/NOMS57970.2025.11073626>.
- RC3.C11** Diego Abreu; Arthur Pimentel; Christian Esteve Rothenberg; Antônio Abelém. **“Two-Stage Deep Q Learning Routing in Entanglement Networks”**. In 30th IEEE Symposium on Computers and Communications (ISCC), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISCC65549.2025.11326361>.
- RC3.C12** Arthur J Simas, Christian Esteve Rothenberg. **“Exploring Neuromorphic Paradigms in Softwarized Networks: A Preliminary Study”**. In 11th IEEE International Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/NetSoft64993.2025.11080565>.
- RC3.C13** Francisco Germano Vogt, Marcelo Caggiani Luizelli, Christian Esteve Rothenberg. **“The Offloading Dilemma: Exploring the Boundaries of Programmable Data Planes”**. In 11th IEEE International Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/NetSoft64993.2025.11080621>.
- RC3.C14** Alireza Shirmarz, Ariel G. de Castro, Fabio L. Verdi, Christian E. Rothenberg. **“CGReplay: Capture and Replay of Cloud Gaming Traffic for QoE/QoS Assessment”**. In 11th IEEE International Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15856056>.
- RC3.C15** Sérgio Rossi Brito da Silva, Francisco Germano Vogt, Marcelo Caggiani Luizelli, Fabricio Rodriguez Cesen, Flávio Geraldo Coelho Rocha, Christian Esteve Rothenberg. **“P4Timely: Evaluating Time Synchronization Resilience in Programmable Networks”**. In 11th IEEE International Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/NETSOFT64993.2025.11080560>.
- RC3.C16** Alan Teixeira da Silva, Fabricio E. Rodriguez Cesen, Md Tariqul Islam, Rafael P. Silva Clerici, Vanessa Testoni, Christian Esteve Rothenberg. **“Assessing QoE in Edge-Delivered Holographic Streaming with a Programmable Hardware Testbed”**. In 11th IEEE International Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/NetSoft64993.2025.11080613>.
- RC3.C17** Filipo Gabert Costa, Francisco Germano Vogt, Fabricio Rodriguez Cesen, Suneet Kumar Singh, Marcelo Caggiani Luizelli, Christian Esteve Rothenberg. **“P4DMA: Unlocking High-Performance RDMA Traffic Generation on Programmable Switches”**. In 11th IEEE International Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/NetSoft64993.2025.11080583>.
- RC3.C18** Francisco Germano Vogt, Victor H. S. Lopes, Fabricio Rodriguez, Marcelo Caggiani Luizelli, Chrysa Papagianni, Christian Rothenberg. **“The GhostTwin: Towards Live Digital Twins via SmartNIC Network Emulation”**. In ACM SIGCOMM Posters and Demos '25: Proceedings of the ACM SIGCOMM 2025 Posters and Demos (SIGCOMM), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3744969.3748450>.
- RC3.C19** Francisco Germano Vogt, Victor H. S. Lopes, Marcelo Caggiani Luizelli, Christian Rothenberg, Gergely Pongracz, Chrysa Papagianni. **“FlexUP: Breaking Up the CU-UP to Speed Up the RAN”**. In ACM SIGCOMM Posters and Demos '25: Proceedings of the ACM SIGCOMM 2025 Posters and Demos (SIGCOMM), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3744969.3748447>.
- RC3.C20** Mauricio Rodriguez, Ariel Goes de Castro, Ramon Fontes, Fabricio Rodriguez, Christian Rothenberg. **“An Integrated Framework for Network Emulation and Multi-vehicle Algorithm Testing”**. In ACM SIGCOMM Posters and Demos '25: Proceedings of the ACM SIGCOMM 2025 Posters and Demos (SIGCOMM), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3744969.3748436>.

- RC3.C21** Alireza Shirmarz, Ariel Goes de Castro, Victor Hugo Schneider Lopes, Fabio Verdi, Marcelo Luizelli, Christian Rothenberg. **“CGSynth: Cloud Gaming Synthesizer”**. In ACM SIGCOMM Posters and Demos '25: Proceedings of the ACM SIGCOMM 2025 Posters and Demos (SIGCOMM), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3744969.3748445>.
- RC3.C22** Everson Borges, Fabricio Rodriguez, Rafael Silva Guimarães, Magnos Martinello, Cristina K. Dominicini, Moises R. N. Ribeiro, Eduard Marin, Christian Rothenberg. **“CRC4EVER: Cyclic Redundancy Check for Enhanced Verification and Efficient Routing”**. In ACM SIGCOMM Posters and Demos '25: Proceedings of the ACM SIGCOMM 2025 Posters and Demos (SIGCOMM), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3744969.3748446>.
- RC3.C23** Francisco Germano Vogt, Christian Rothenberg, Victor H. S. Lopes, Marcelo Caggiani Luizelli, Fabricio Rodriguez, Chrysa Papagianni, Gergely Pongrácz. **“DEMO: SmartNet: Bridging Performance and Realism in Network Emulation with SmartNICs”**. In ACM SIGCOMM Posters and Demos '25: Proceedings of the ACM SIGCOMM 2025 Posters and Demos (SIGCOMM), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3744969.3748449>.
- RC3.C24** Flavio G C Rocha, Kleber V Cardoso, Murillo Melo, Jonathas dos Santos, Lorenzo Chiachio, Vlademir Brusse, Fabio Luciano Verdi, Leandro Almeida, Cristiano Bonato Both, Andre Mendes Cavalcante, Maria Marquezini, Pedro Henrique Gomes. **“Zero-Lag Smart Pipes for Smart Factories: AI-Driven Programmable Transport in Open RAN”**. In 21st International Conference on Network and Service Management (CNSM), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17527127>.
- RC3.C25** Ramon Fontes, Eduardo Cerqueira, Christian Rothenberg. **“Wmediumd for 802.15.4: Bridging the Gap Between Simulation and Physical Testbeds”**. In 21st International Conference on Network and Service Management (CNSM), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17781971>.
- RC3.C26** Marcelo Basso, Vinícius B. Alves, Laura B. Ramos, Julien Guillemot, André Riker, Antônio Abelém, Luciano Gaspar, Mohamed Faten Zhani, Jaime Galan-Jimenez, **“Bringing Programmable Low-End Networks to Life: A Field Study with an Off-the-Shelf Prototype”**. In IEEE/IFIP Network Operations and Management (NOMS), 2025. Symposium DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/NOMS57970.2025.11073634>.
- RC3.C27** Francisco Germano Vogt, Zhiheng Yang, Victor Hugo Schneider Lopes, Fabricio Rodriguez, Marcelo Caggiani Luizelli, Christian Esteve Rothenberg, Chrysa Papagianni. **“Poster: Reconstructing LLM Training Workloads: A Topology- and Model-aware Network Tester”**. In CoNEXT '25: Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on emerging Networking EXperiments and Technologies (CONEXT), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3765515.3771757>.
- RC3.C28** Francisco Germano Vogt, Zhiheng Yang, Victor Hugo Schneider Lopes, Fabricio Rodriguez, Marcelo Caggiani Luizelli, Christian Esteve Rothenberg, Chrysa Papagianni. **“Poster: QueuePilot: Towards Adaptive Queue Scheduling via Live Digital Twins”**. In CoNEXT '25: Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on emerging Networking EXperiments and Technologies (CONEXT), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3765515.3771755>.
- RC3.C29** Zhiheng Yang, Francisco Vogt, Adam Belloum, Christian Rothenberg, Paola Grosso, Chrysa Papagianni. **“Adaptive Digital Twin Synchronization: A Mechanism for Where, When, and What to Measure”**. In CoNEXT-SW '25: Proceedings of the CoNEXT'25 Student workshop (CONEXT), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3769700.3771695>.
- RC3.C30** Raza Ul Mustafa, Md Tariqul Islam, Roi Dupart, Noman Ashraf, Christian Esteve Rothenberg. **“Mobile 360° Video QoE: Measurement, Emulation, and GAN-Driven Throughput Synthesis”**. In The 27th International Conference on Modeling, Analysis and Simulation of Wireless and Mobile Systems (MSWiM), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17825050>.

- RC3.C31** Cesar Bastos da Silva, Maria Fernanda Paulino Gomes, Vitor Rodrigues Zanata da Silva, Eric Rohmer. **“From Utensil Grasping to Food Transfer: A Learning-Based Framework for Robotic Feeding”**. In IEEE/RSJ International (IROS), 2025. on Conference DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17825580>.
- RC3.C32** Leonel Feitosa, Vandirleya Barbosa, Luis Guilherme Silva, Iure Fé, Fabíola M. C. de Oliveira, Luiz Fernando Bittencourt, Huber Flores, Francisco Ailton Silva. **“Modeling Drone Deliveries Using Petri Nets: An Evaluation on Collision Recovery and Energy Efficiency”**. In IEEE International Conference on Systems, and Cybernetics DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17825386>.
- RC3.C33** Heictor Alves de Oliveira Costa, Fernando José Von Zuben. **“Optimizing Energy Efficiency in Agricultural Spraying Drones Through Fractional-Order PID Controllers and Genetic Algorithm”**. In International Symposium (ISE), DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17904788>.
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- RC3.C35** Diego Medeiros de Abreu, Antônio Abelém. **“Towards Blind Quantum Machine Learning in Entanglement Networks”**. In Proceedings of the 2nd Workshop on Quantum Networks and Distributed Quantum Computing (QuNet '25), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3749096.3750027>.
- RC3.C36** Diego Abreu, Arthur Pimentel, Antônio Abelém. **“Q-CAST Mobility: Multipath Routing Protocol for Mobile Quantum Networks”**. In 2025 International Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing (IWCMC), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/IWCMC65282.2025.11059645>.
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- RC3.C38** Marcos P. A. Dal Maso; Andrés F. Escallón-Portilla; Kayol S. Mayer; Isabela M. da Silva; Darli A. A. Mello; Dalton S. Arantes; Christian E. Rothenberg. **“Pinpointing Faulty Optical Amplifiers: Unsupervised Learning on Real Telemetry Data”**. In 25th Anniversary International Conference on Transparent Optical Networks (ICTON), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICTON67126.2025.11125419>.
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- RC3.C40** E. J. Santos and T. A. Almeida, **“From Statistics to Deep Learning: Forecasting Mobile Throughput,”** The 13th Symposium on Knowledge Discovery, Mining and Learning (KDMiLe'25), Fortaleza, Brazil, 2025, pp. 1-8, doi: <https://doi.org/10.5753/kdmile.2025.247767>.

D) Papers presented at Brazilian conferences

- RC3.D01** Mauricio Rodriguez Cesen, Ariel Goes de Castro, Ibini A. Santana, Ramon R. Fontes, Fabricio R. Cesen, Christian Esteve Rothenberg. **“UNetyEmu: Unity-based simulator for aerial and non-aerial vehicles with integrated network emulation”**. In 2025: Anais Estendidos do XLIII Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos (SBRC), 2025. DOI: https://doi.org/10.5753/sbrc_estendido.2025.7122.

- RC3.D02** Rodrigo A. de A. Pierini, Caio Teixeira, Christian Esteve Rothenberg, Marco Amaral Henriques. “**Implementação e avaliação da cifra de fluxo Xote em plano de dados de hardware programável Tofino**”. In 2025: Anais Estendidos do XLIII Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5753/sbrc.2025.6337>.
- RC3.D03** Alan Teixeira da Silva, Fabricio R. Cesen, Rafael Clerici, Christian E. Rothenberg, Eduardo Cerqueira, Vanessa Testoni. “**Ambiente Programável para Transmissão e Análise de Qualidade de Experiência de Vídeo Volumétrico**”. In 2025: Anais Estendidos do XLIII Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos (SBRC), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5753/sbrc.2025.6365>.
- RC3.D04** Alireza Shirmarz, Fabricio R. Cesen, Fábio Luciano Verdi, Roberto Silva Netto, Suneet Kumar Singh, Christian Esteve Rothenberg. “**DCTPQ: Dynamic Cloud Gaming Traffic Prioritization Using Machine Learning and Multi-Queueing for QoE Enhancement**”. In 2025: Anais Estendidos do XLIII Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos (SBRC), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5753/sbrc.2025.6266>.
- RC3.D05** Diego Abreu, David Moura, Christian Rothenberg, Antônio Abelém. “**Rede Generativa Adversarial Quântica Semi-Supervisionada (sQGAN) para Detecção de Ataques**”. In 2025: Anais Estendidos do XLIII Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos (SBRC), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5753/sbrc.2025.5901>.
- RC3.D06** Leonel Feitosa, Vandırleya Barbosa, Luiz Fernando Bittencourt, Fabíola M. C. de Oliveira, José Valdemir R. Junior e Francisco Airtton Silva. “**Entregas Aéreas por Drones: Uma Avaliação de Desempenho Considerando Colisões dos drones e Logística de Reparo**”. In 2025: Anais do XLIII Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos (SBRC), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5753/sbrc.2025.6317>.
- RC3.D07** Heictor Alves de Oliveira Costa, Fernando José Von Zuben. “**Hybrid Offline-Online UAV Optimal Path Planning and Outbreak Dynamic Autonomous Behavior**”. Anais do XVII Congresso Brasileiro de Inteligência Computacional (CBIC), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21528/CBIC2025-1175935>.
- RC3.D08** Diego Abreu, Arthur Pimentel, Antônio Abelém. “**Redes Quânticas Sob Ataque: Black Hole Repeaters**”. In 2025: Anais Estendidos do XLIII Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos (SBRC), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5753/sbrc.2025.5902>.
- RC3.D09** David Tavares, Diego Abreu, Polyana Moraes, Arthur Pimentel, Antônio Abelém. “**Estratégia de Agendamento de Purificação Híbrida para Redes Quânticas de Canais Ruidosos Heterogêneos**”. In 2025: Anais Estendidos do XLIII Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos (SBRC), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5753/sbrc.2025.5904>.
- RC3.D10** Diego Abreu, Antônio Abelém. “**Ataques de Repetidores em Redes de Entrelaçamento Quântico**”. In 2025: Anais do II Workshop de Redes Quânticas (WQUNETS), DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5753/wqunets.2025.8770>.
- RC3.D11** Fernando N. N. Farias, Diego Abreu, Antônio J. G. Abelém. “**Proposta de Open RAN Seguras Através de Distribuição De Chaves Quânticas Criptográficas em Redes QKDs Definidas Por Software**”. In 2025: Anais do 2025. Workshop II de Redes Quânticas (WQUNETS), DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5753/wqunets.2025.9504>.
- RC3.D12** Charles F. Santos, Augusto V. Neto, Ramon R. Fontes, Roger Immich, Vicente Sousa Jr., Helber W. da Silva. “**Predictive OMS Switchover towards Proactive Disaster Recovery in 5G Networks**”. In 2025: Anais Estendidos do XLIII Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos (SBRC), 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5753/sbrc.2025.6402>.

RC3.D13 Hiago Vinícius Benedito dos Santos, Raissa Rosa dos Santos Januario, Ravelly Carvalho Zanatta, Saulo Neves Matos, Jó Ueyama. **“Comparative Analysis of Smart Contract Generation Using Large Language Models”**. In 2025: Anais Estendidos do XLIII Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e (SBRC), Distribuídos Sistemas DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5753/sbrc.2025.5848>.

RC3.D14 Rodrigo Duarte de Meneses, Marco Amaral Henriques. **“Scalable Batch Verification for Post-Quantum Hash-Based Signatures Using STARKs”**. In 2025: Anais Estendidos do XXV Simpósio Brasileiro de Cibersegurança. DOI: https://doi.org/10.5753/sbseq_estendido.2025.11845.

E) Patents filed and IvDs submitted

RC3.E01 Patent Reference Number: WIPO GR01 (20250101016)
Authors: Konstantinos Vandikas, Ondrej Smid, Fábio Luciano Verdi, Washington Silva, Guilherme Mendes Vieira de Matos and Andrew Williams
Title: DEPLOYING APPLICATIONS ACROSS HETEROGENEOUS COMPUTING RESOURCES
Status: Filed

H) MSc Dissertations defended

RC3.H01 Lucas Seiki Oshiro. **“Simulação reprodutível de protocolos de comunicação para Smart Grids”**. 2025. Dissertação (Mestrado em Ciência da Computação) - Instituto de Matemática e Estatística, Universidade de São Paulo. <https://doi.org/10.11606/D.45.2025.tde-10012026-174403>.

RC3.H02 Ervin Alain Bolivar Huayhua. **“Integração de LLMs na Otimização e Planejamento de Sistemas Multiagentes IoRT e Interação Conversacional”**. 2025. Dissertação (Mestrado Mestre em Engenharia Elétrica, na área de Automação.) - Faculdade de Engenharia Elétrica e de Computação da Universidade Estadual de Campinas. <https://doi.org/10.47749/T/UNICAMP.2025.1518574>.

RC3.H03 Breno Miranda Portela. **“Prototipagem de um Robô Humanoide com Expressividade Não Verbal para Interação Humano-Robô”**. 2025. Dissertação (Mestrado Mestre em Engenharia Elétrica, na área de Automação.) - Faculdade de Engenharia Elétrica e de Computação da Universidade Estadual de Campinas.

I) PhD Theses defended

RC3.I01 Eduardo de Souza Gama. **“An Architecture for Adaptive Video Streaming: QoE Forecasting, Content Steering, and Scalable Resource Management through Edge-Cloud Computing”**. 2025. Universidade Estadual de Campinas. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47749/T/UNICAMP.2025.1506246>.

J) List of papers prepared, submitted, and accepted for publication

Accepted

RC3.J01 Amath Sow, Mauricio Rodriguez Cesen, Fabíola Martins Campos de Oliveira, Mariusz Wzorek, Daniel de Leng, Mattias Tiger, Fredrik Heintz, Christian Esteve Rothenberg. **“Multi UAVs Preflight Planning in a Shared and Dynamic International Conference on Autonomous Agents and Airspace”**. 25th Multiagent Systems (AAMAS), 2026.

RC3.J02 Heictor Alves de Oliveira Costa, Fernando José Von Zuben. **“Energy-aware Truck-Drone Last-mile Logistics Co-optimized with Distribution Grid Constraints”**. 16th International Conference on Power, Energy, and Electrical Engineering (CPEEE), 2026.

- RC3.J03** V. H. S. Lopes, A. G. de Castro, F. Vogt, F. Rossi, F. E. R. Cesen, C. E. Rothenberg, and M. C. Luizelli. **“Towards Network Agentic AI: Offloading Small Language Models to SmartNICs”**. IEEE/IFIP Network Operations and Management Symposium (NOMS), 2026.
- RC3.J04** M. T. Islam and C. E. Rothenberg. **“Why Realistic Background Traffic Matters: Low-Latency Transport Evaluation with MATGen”**. IEEE/IFIP Network Operations and Management Symposium (NOMS), 2026.
- RC3.J05** Andrea Caruso, Públío Elon Correa da Silva, Christian Grasso, Giovanni Schembra. **“DT-Based Cloud Gaming in Softwarized Networks to Enable Players in Developing Countries”**. IEEE Symposium on Computers and Communications (ISCC), 2025.
- RC3.J06** Vogt, F. G., Lopes, V. H. S., Luizelli, M. C., Rothenberg, C. E., Pongrácz, G., & Papagianni, C. **“FlexUP: Breaking Up the CU-UP to Speed Up the RAN.”** IEEE NetSoft 2026, Feb. 2026.
- RC3.J07** S. K. Singh, S. G. Grøsvik, M. Gajić, C. E. Rothenberg, S. Lange, and T. Zinner. **“From Prediction to Action: Real-Time QoE-Aware RAN Control for 5G and Beyond”**. NetSoft26 Submitted to IEEE NetSoft 2026, Feb. 2026.
- RC3.J13** Gustavo Spadotto Jardim, Bruno Oliveira Silvestre, Kleber Vieira Cardoso, Matheus Pires, Sand Luz Correa, Fábio Verdi, Cristiano Bonato Both. **“Enforcing Service Stability for WebAssembly Extended Reality Workloads at the Edge: A Quality of Service Aware Orchestration Framework”**. 44o. Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos (SBRC 2026).
- RC3.J14** Públío Elon Correa da Silva, Fábio Luciano Verdi. **“Avaliação de Estimadores de Largura de Banda e Impactos em Aplicações de Vídeo 360° em Tempo Real”**. 44o. Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos (SBRC 2026).
- RC3.J15** Lucas Jaiel de Sousa Correia, Alireza Shirmarz, Fábio Luciano Verdi, Paulo Ditarso Maciel Jr., Leandro C. de Almeida. **“When ECN Lies: Unfairness and Exploitation in L4S Architectures”**. 44o. Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos (SBRC 2026).
- RC3.J16** Mina Kaviani, Jurandy Almeida, Ricardo Souza, Fábio Luciano Verdi. **“Multi-Task Learning Architectures for Joint Interference Detection and KPI Prediction in 5G Networks”**. 44o. Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos (SBRC 2026).
- RC3.J17** Rafael Chaves, Rebeca Cabral, João Paulo Esper, Rafael Rodrigues Silva, Kleber Vieira Cardoso, Leandro C. de Almeida, Ruan Delgado Gomes, Fábio Luciano Verdi. **“Intento, logo programa: Uma camada de agentes para traduzir prompts em chamadas para a API de operações do núcleo 5G”**. 44o. Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos (SBRC 2026).
- RC3.J18** Johny Marques Borges Ribeiro, Konstantinos Vandikas, Maria Valéria Marquezini, Christian Esteve Rothenberg, Rafael Pasquini. **“An Experimental Framework for Studying Non-IID Data in Federated Learning for Network Telemetry”**. 44o. Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos (SBRC 2026).
- RC3.J19** Rafael Rodrigues Silva, João Paulo Esper, Kleber Vieira Cardoso, Rafael Chaves, Leandro C. de Almeida, Fábio Luciano Verdi. **“C2N: Bridging CAMARA Service APIs and 3GPP Core Network Exposure Function”**. 44o. Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos (SBRC 2026).

- RC3.J23** Washington Rodrigo Dias da Silva. **“SPARX: A Resource-aware Partitioning Framework for Distributed Inference on Heterogeneous Devices”**. Sigmetrics 2026 Student Research Competition (SRC).
- RC3.J24** Guilherme Mendes Vieira de Matos. **“Toward End-to-End Adaptive Application Decomposition and Execution Across Distributed Computing Infrastructures”**. Sigmetrics 2026 Student Research Competition (SRC).
- RC3.J38** Mateus C. Oliveira, Heitor H. da Silva, Camilo H. M. dos Santos, Carlos Senna, Allan M. de Souza, Luiz F. Bittencourt. **“LoRA-SL: Low-Rank Adaptation for Continual Split Learning”**. 44o. Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos (SBRC 2026).
- RC3.J42** José Miqueias, Lucas Silva Lopes, Iure Fé, Jonas Nunes, Luiz Fernando Bittencourt, Juliano Wickboldt e Francisco Airton Silva. **“Drones-DT: Gerenciamento Dinâmico de Frotas de Drones Representados por Gêmeos Digitais”**. 44o. Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos (SBRC 2026).

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- RC3.J08** A. Shirmarz, A. G. de Castro, V. H. S. Lopes, F. L. Verdi, S. Ferlin, C. E. Rothenberg, and M. C. Luizelli. **“QoE Comparison from Real to Synthetic: Cloud Gaming Traffic Generation and QoE Modeling.”** Submitted to Transactions on Multimedia Computing Communications and Applications (TOMM), Feb. 2026.
- RC3.J09** Marina Martinelli, Christian Esteve Rothenberg, André Tosi Furtado. **“Dinâmicas de Desenvolvimento e Difusão do Conhecimento em Redes 5G/6G Aplicadas a Smart Grids e Microgrids Globalmente e no Brasil”**. Submitted to Cadernos do Desenvolvimento, Centro Celso Furtado, Scielo, Oct. 2025.
- RC3.J10** Marina Martinelli, André Tosi Furtado, Christian Esteve Rothenberg. **“Technological Innovation System in Extended Reality with 5G en route to 6G: Global Assessment and Spanish Case (2014-2024)”**. Submitted to World Patent Information, Elsevier, Nov. 2025.
- RC3.J11** Marina Martinelli, Christian Esteve Rothenberg, André Tosi Furtado. **“Knowledge Flow on Smart and Microgrids with 5G/6G Technologies: Global and Brazilian Perspectives (2019–2023)”**. Submitted to Revista Brasileira de Inovação, Scielo, May. 2025
- RC3.J12** Matheus Pires, Gabriel Espindola, Gustavo Jardim, Andrew Williams, Ondrej Smid, Héctor Caltenco, Cristiano Both, Bruno Silvestre, Kleber Cardoso, Fábio Verdi, Sand Correa. **“Wasm-EEL: Computational Offloading for Mobile Devices over Edge Computing Enabler Layer”**. Submitted to IEEE Communications Magazine, Feb 2026.
- RC3.J20** Alireza Shirmarz, Gyanesh Patra, Gergely Pongrácz, Fábio Luciano Verdi. **“NICoLE: Are In-Network LLM-Based Agents Cost-Feasible for RTP Video Streaming?”** Submitted to IFIP Networking 2026.
- RC3.J21** Mina Kaviani, Jurandy Almeida, Ricardo Souza, Fábio Luciano Verdi. **“On the Effectiveness of Multi-Task Learning for 5G RAN Modeling: A Comparative Study with Single-Task Approaches”**. Submitted to IFIP Networking 2026.
- RC3.J22** Gabriel Santos de Andrade, Leandro Almeida, Chrysa Papagianni, Fábio Luciano Verdi. **“Evaluating the Impact of Lightweight INT on the Usage of Machine Learning for QoS Prediction: A Side Effect Analysis”**. Submitted to IFIP Networking 2026.
- RC3.J25** Israel da Silva Barros, Fabíola Martins Campos de Oliveira, Luiz F. Bittencourt, Carlos A. Kamienski. **“Collision-Aware UAV Delivery via Learning-Based Autonomous Control”**. Submitted to Expert Systems with Applications (ESWA), Mar 2026.

- RC3.J26** R. Fontes, E. Cerqueira, C. Rothenberg, and P. Mendes. **"Mininet-X: A Unified Emulator for Satellite and Aeronautical Ad Hoc Networks"**. Submitted to Transactions on Modeling and Computer Simulation (TOMACS), Feb. 2026.
- RC3.J27** Erick Aparecido Escagion, Rossano Pablo Pinto, Christian Esteve Rothenberg. **"YangToTestFW: Uma Ferramenta para Geração de Testes para a partir de Especificações YANG"**. Submitted to SBRC-Salão de Ferramentas (SBRC-SF 2026).
- RC3.J28** F. Vogt, L. H. Guimarães, Z. Yang, S. R. da Silva, M. C. Luizelli, C. Papagianni, and C. Rothenberg. **"GhostView: Enabling Deep Visibility in Programmable Data Planes with Minimal Server Overhead"**. Submitted to SBRC-Salão de Ferramentas (SBRC-SF 2026)
- RC3.J29** F. Vogt, Z. Yang, L. H. Guimarães, S. R. da Silva, C. Papagianni, M. C. Luizelli, and C. Rothenberg. **"P4R: Scaling Stateful Network Testing and Trace Replay with Nanosecond-level Accuracy"**. Submitted to SBRC-Salão de Ferramentas (SBRC-SF 2026)
- RC3.J30** S. R. da Silva, F. Vogt, F. Rocha, M. C. Luizelli, C. Papagianni, and C. Rothenberg. **"Expanding TFTG: Multi-flow Generation and Credit-Based Shaping for Deterministic Networks"**. Submitted to SBRC-Salão de Ferramentas (SBRC-SF 2026).
- RC3.J31** Flávio G. C. Rocha, Kleber V. Cardoso, Cristiano B. Both, Fábio L. Verdi, Leandro C. de Almeida, Jonathas dos Santos, Lorenzo Chiachio, Murillo P. T. Melo, Vlademir Brusse, André M. Cavalcante, Maria V. Marquezini, Pedro H. Gomes. **"Federated ANFIS-Based Resource Allocation in Sliced Open RAN Transport Networks for Smart Factory Applications"**. Submitted to IEEE Transactions on Cognitive Communications and Networking, Oct. 2025.
- RC3.J32** S. R. da Silva, F. Vogt, F. Rocha, M. C. Luizelli, C. Papagianni, and C. Rothenberg. **"Expanding TFTG: Multi-flow Generation and Credit-Based Shaping for Deterministic Networks"**. Submitted to SBRC-Salão de Ferramentas (SBRC-SF 2026).
- RC3.J33** OSHIRO, Lucas; FERNANDES, Natalia Castro; BATISTA, Daniel M.: **"GridGooseSV: um Módulo do NS-3 para Simular Protocolos de Comunicação de Smart Grids definidos na IEC 61850"**. Submitted to SBRC-Salão de Ferramentas (SBRC-SF 2026), 2026
- RC3.J34** E. K. Cruz Ortega, Eduardo Sandalo Porto, Ana C. V. de Melo, Daniel Macêdo Batista, **"Integrating NWDAF and Federated Learning for Privacy-Preserving Intrusion Detection in B5G IoHT Networks"**. Submitted to IEEE Networking Letters, 2026
- RC3.J35** Dos Anjos, Giovanna Luisa Hirata; Macêdo Batista, Daniel. **"Detecção de Intrusões em Tráfego DNS utilizando Redes Neurais e Explicabilidade"**. Submitted to SBRC-Workshop de Trabalhos de Iniciação Científica e de Graduação (SBRC-WTG 2026), 2026
- RC3.J37** Milena F. Silva, Heitor H. da Silva, Mateus C. Oliveira, Carlos Senna, Allan M. de Souza, Juliana F. Borin, Luiz F. Bittencourt. **"Split Computing for Vehicle Detection in Smart Parking"**. 44o. Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos (Submitted to the Workshop de Computação Urbana 2026).
- RC3.J39** Vogt, F., Bragatto, M., Lopes, V. H. S., Rodriguez, F., Marin, E., Schmid, S., Verdi, F. L., Luizelli, M., Pongrácz, G., Rothenberg, C., & Papagianni, C. **"GhostQueues: Virtualizing Queue Semantics Beyond Hardware Limits."** Submitted to SIGCOMM 2026, Jan. 2026.
- RC3.J40** Vogt, F., Lopes, V. H. S., Rodriguez, F., Yang, Z., Pongrácz, G., Patra, P. G. K., Rossi, F., Costa Filho, R. I. T., Rothenberg, C., Papagianni, C., & Luizelli, M. **"GhostTwin: Enabling Live Network Digital Twin on Programmable Networks."** Submitted to

SIGCOMM 2026, Jan. 2026.

- RC3.J41** Capovilla, F., Rodriguez, M., Rothenberg, C. "**UNetyEmuROS: A Unity-Based Multi-Vehicle Simulator with Physically-Grounded Dynamics and ROS2 Sensor Integration**". Submitted to SBRC-Salão de Ferramentas (SBRC-SF 2026).
- RC3.J43** Goes de Castro, A., Vandikas K., Ferlin, S., Chiesa, M., Rothenberg, C. "**OperAID: Benchmarking LLM Agents for Autonomous Kubernetes Fault Remediation**". Submitted to IEEE NetSoft workshop Trust 6G-Net: Trust for Service Oriented 6G Network Architecture 2026.
- RC3.J45** F. G. Costa, F. Rodriguez, F. Vogt, M. C. Luizelli, and C. Rothenberg, "**QU4C: Towards Reproducing QUIC traffic on a P4-based Programmable Switch**". Submitted to IEEE NetSoft 2026 Posters.
- RC3.J46** Andrew Williams, Srinivasa Vinay Yadhav, Ondrej Smid, Sai Chandrasekar, Guilherme Mendes Vieira de Matos, Shilpa Budhka. "**Elastic Runtime for Distributed WebAssembly Components**". 38th European Conference on Real-Time Systems, Track: Industrial Challenge.
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V. List of Abbreviations

3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
6G	6th Generation
ABNT	Associação Brasileira de Normas Técnicas (Brazilian Association of Technical Standards)
ACM	Association for Computing Machinery
ADVENTURE	Adaptive and Secure Network Applications over the Industrial Internet
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AKMA	Authentication and Key Management for Applications
AMQP	Advanced Message Queuing Protocol
ANATEL	Agência Nacional de Telecomunicações (National Telecommunications Agency)
ANFIS	Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
B5G	Beyond 5G
BC	Benefício Complementar (Complementary Benefit)
BEPE	Scholarship for Research Internship Abroad
C3LA	Cognitive Closed Control Loops Architecture for Edge IoV Services
CA	Cognitive Architectures
CAD	Computer-Aided Design
CCL	Closed Control Loop
CEC	Customized Edge Computing
CCEN	Center for Exact and Natural Sciences
CG	Cloud Gaming
CISB	Brazil-Sweden Research and Innovation Centre
Co-PI	Co-Principal Investigator
CPE	Centro de Pesquisa em Engenharia (Engineering Research Center - ERC)
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DEMIST	Distributed Edge Computing Swarm Intelligence
DisCoNet	Distributed Computer Networking
DMTF	Distributed Management Task Force
DP	Differential Privacy
DPDK	Data Plane Development Kit
DPU	Data Processing Unit
DR	Doctorate
DT	Decision Tree
eBPF	Extended Berkeley Packet Filter
EAIP	Escritório de Apoio Institucional ao Pesquisador (Institutional Support Office for Researchers)
EC	Executive Committee
ECN	Explicit Congestion Notification
MBB	Mobile Broadband
EDC	Education and Dissemination Coordinator
EDD	Education and Dissemination Deputy
EDK	Education and Dissemination of Knowledge
EDKM	Education and Dissemination of Knowledge Manager
EM	Executive Manager
EPC	Evolved Packet Core
EPM	Executive Project Management
ER	Ericsson Research
ERC	Engineering Research Center
EU	European Union
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
FAPESP	Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado de São Paulo (São Paulo Research Foundation)
FCD	Fluid Control and Data Planes
FL	Federated Learning

FPGA	Field-Programmable Gate Array
GAN	Generative Adversarial Networks
GEO	Management, Structure, and Governance Plan
GO	Grant Office
GOOSE	Generic Object Oriented System Event
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HTC	Holographic-Type Communications
HW	Hardware
IAB	International Advisory Board
IBN	Intent-Based Networking
IC	Iniciação Científica” (Undergraduate Researcher)
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission's
IED	Intelligent Electronic Device
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IIIT	Indian Institute of Information Technology
INT	In-band Network Telemetry
INOVA	UNICAMP Innovation Agency
INPI	Instituto Nacional da Propriedade Industrial (National Institute of Industrial Property)
INT	n-Band Network Telemetry
IoHT	Internet of Holographic Things
IoRT	Internet of Robotic Things
IoT	Internet of Things
IoV	Internet of Vehicles
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IR	Intermediary Representations
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ITC	International Teletraffic Congress
ITS	Intelligent Transport Systems
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
ITU-T	International Telecommunication Union - Telecommunication Standardization Sector
IvD	Invention Disclosure
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
kTLS	kernel Transport Layer Security
L4S	Low Latency, Low Loss, Scalable Throughput
LCA	Laboratory of Control and Automation
LEMAC	Laboratory of Applied and Computational Electromagnetism
LLM	Large Language Model
LGPD	Brazilian General Data Protection Law
MAR	Mobile Augmented Reality
MBB	Mobile Broadband
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
MIMO	Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
ML	Machine Learning
MMS	Manufacturing Message Specification
MNS	Multiscale Network Systems
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
MSc	Master of Sciences
NEWTON	iN Edge netWork indusTrial automatioN
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NOMS	Network Operations and Management Symposium
NSF	National Science Foundation
NTR	Nothing To Report
NWDAF	Network Data Analytics Function

ONF	Open Networking Foundation
ONAP	Open Network Automation Platform
ONF	Open Networking Foundation
O-RAN	Open Radio Access Network
P4	Programming Protocol-independent Packet Processors
PA	In Portuguese “Pesquisador Associado”, in English “Associate Researcher”
PCAP	Packet Capture
PCT	Patent Cooperation Treaty
PD	In Portuguese “Pesquisador de Doutorado”, in English “Doctoral Researcher”
PI	Principal Investigator
PIPE	Support Program for Research in Small Businesses
PITE	Research Partnership for Technological Innovation Program
PP	In Portuguese “Pesquisador Principal”, in English “Principal Researcher”
PPC	Partnership Coordinator
PPDG	Postdoctoral Scholarship Subprogram in Research Management
PoC	Proof of Concept
PRP	Pro-Rectorate of Research
PTT	Plan for Technology Transfer
QKD	Quantum Key Distribution
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
QUIC	Quick UDP Internet Connections
RAN	Radio Access Network
RA	Research Area
RC1	Second SMARTNESS Scientific Report
REDK2	Second SMARTNESS Education and Dissemination of Knowledge Report
RF	Radiofrequency
RGE02	Second SMARTNESS Governance Report
RIC	RAN Intelligent Controller
RL	Reinforcement Learning
RNP	PT: “Rede Nacional de Ensino e Pesquisa”; ENG: “Brazilian network for education and research”
RL	Reinforcement Learning
ROS2	Robot Operating System 2
RS	Research Strand
RTT2	Second SMARTNESS Technology Transfer Report
SA	Stand Alone
SAGe	FAPESP online system
SAM	Humanoid Agent
SBOM	Software Bill of Materials
SBRC	Brazilian Symposium on Computer Networks
SCI	UNICAMP Institutional Communication Secretariat
SEM	SMARTNESS Entanglement Meetings
SDN	Software-Defined Networking
SFC	Service Function Chaining
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SLAM	Simultaneous Localization and Mapping
SLSA	Supply Chain Levels for Software Artifacts
SMARTNESS	Smart Networks and Services for 2030
SmartNIC	Smart Network Interface Card
SMO	Service Management and Orchestration
SNS	Smart Networks and Services
SPDM	Security Protocol and Data Model
SS5G	SMARTNESS Studio 5G
SS5GTF	SMARTNESS Studio 5G Task Force

STA	Scientific and Technology Advancement
STAB	STA Board
SUS	Sustainability
SV	Sampled Values
SW	Software
TBD	To Be Defined
TDRP	Truck-Drone Routing Problem
TFHE	Fast Fully Homomorphic Encryption over the Torus
TLS	Transport Layer Security
TROCA	Transportation Robotic Cognitive Architecture
TPU	Tensor Processing Unit
TRU	Trustworthiness: Security, Privacy, Safety, Ethics
TSN	Time-Sensitive Networking
TT	Technology Transfer
TTC	Technology Transfer Coordinator
TTD	Technology Transfer Deputy
TTI	Technology Transfer and Innovation
TTM	Technology Transfer Manager
TSN	Time-Sensitive Networking
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UFABC	Federal University of ABC
UFAM	Federal University of Amazonas
UFBA	Federal University of Bahia
UFC	Federal University of Ceará
UFCG	Federal University of Campina Grande
UFES	Federal University of Espírito Santo
UFF	Fluminense Federal University
UFG	Federal University of Goiás
UFMG	Federal University of Minas Gerais
UNICAMP	Universidade Estadual de Campinas (State University of Campinas)
UNIPAMPA	Universidade Federal do Pampa
UNISINOS	Universidade do Vale do Rio dos Sinos
UFPA	Federal University of Pará
UFPE	Federal University of Pernambuco
UFRGS	Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul
UFRN	Federal University of Rio Grande do Norte
UFSCar	Federal University of São Carlos
UFSC	Federal University of Santa Catarina
UFU	Federal University of Uberlândia
UG	Undergrad
UE	User Equipment
UPF	User Plane Function
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable and Low-Latency Communications
USP	Universidade Estadual de São Paulo (State University of São Paulo)
VR	Virtual Reality
VNA	Vector Network Analyzer
WASM	WebAssembly
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package
XR	Extended Reality
YANG	Yet Another Next Generation (Data Modeling Language)